

ASILE

Global Asylum
Governance and
the European
Union's Role

The Right of Asylum in Comparative Regional Perspectives

Access, Procedures and Protection

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AALCO	Asian-African Legal Consultative Organization
ACHR	American Convention on Human Rights
ACHPR	African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights
ACtHPR	African Court on Human and People's Rights
African Charter	African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights
Arab Charter	Arab Charter on Human Rights
AU	African Union
CEAS	Common European Asylum System
CJEU	Court of Justice of the European Union
CoE	Council of Europe
CUP	Cambridge University Press
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EMN	European Migration Network
ETS	European Treaty Series
EU	European Union
EUAPD	EU Asylum Procedures Directive
EUCFR	EU Charter on Fundamental Rights
EU Dublin III	EU Dublin Regulation
EUQD	EU Qualification Directive
EURCD	EU Reception Conditions Directive
EURD	EU Return Directive
EUTPD	EU Temporary Protection Directive
GCR	Global Compact on Refugees

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HAP	Humanitarian Admission Program
IACHR	Inter-American Commission of Human Rights
IACtHR	Inter-American Court of Human Rights
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICESCR	International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
ICJ	International Court of Justice
IFA	Internal Flight Alternative
LAS	League of Arab States
OAU	Organisation of African Unity
OUP	Oxford University Press
Refugee Convention	1951 Refugee Convention relating to the Status of Refugees
TEU	Treaty on European Union
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNTS	United Nations Treaty Series

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 Background

This working paper provides an account of regional standards on the right of asylum, with a focus on protection systems in Europe, the Americas and Africa – the three regions with binding regional and sub-regional protection regimes.¹ In setting out regional protection regimes, the working paper focuses on legal standards governing the right of asylum in countries central to the ASILE project covered by these regional regimes, namely Brazil, Canada, South Africa and Turkey. As neither the Asia-Pacific nor the Middle East have binding regional instruments for the protection of refugees, relevant regional soft law instruments are briefly addressed, with respect to ASILE focus countries Bangladesh and Jordan.

The working paper is set against the background of the Global Compact on Refugees (GCR), a non-binding instrument grounded in the international refugee regime, most notably the 1951 *Convention on the Status of Refugees* ('Refugee Convention') and its 1967 Protocol.² The GCR aims to provide a 'basis for predictable and equitable burden- and responsibility-sharing' for refugees globally.³ Paragraph 5 of the GCR acknowledges the key role of regional protection instruments to the international refugee regime, with specific reference to the instruments addressed in this working paper.⁴

This working paper is a part of the ASILE Project's research agenda in mapping existing international and regional asylum governance regimes. As such, this working paper follows the recent publication, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards: Refugee and Human Rights Law Standards Applicable to Asylum Governance*.⁵ As a doctrinal legal analysis, the working paper

¹ We warmly thank Joshua Blum, Sergio Carrera, Fatima Khan, Gilberto M.A. Rodriguez and Jens Vedsted-Hansen for their valuable comments on a draft of this working paper. Any errors remain our own.

² Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees (adopted 28 July 1951, entered into force 22 April 1954) 189 UNTS 137 (Refugee Convention)

³ Global Compact on Refugees (UN doc. A/73/12 (Part II), affirmed by Resolution 73/151 of the UN General Assembly, adopted 17 December 2018), para 3.

⁴ Global Compact on Refugees para 5

⁵ Nikolas Feith Tan and Jens Vedsted-Hansen, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards: Refugee and Human Rights Law Standards Applicable to Asylum Governance* (2021).

primarily relies on binding instruments of regional law.⁶ However, non-binding instruments and sources are identified where no binding instrument exists, where they have been implemented in national asylum systems or as an aid to interpretation of binding standards.

The paper's focus lies not with the international law question of an individual right to asylum,⁷ but rather on regional systems providing for the right of asylum, including access to territory, asylum procedures, the scope and content of protection and, in keeping with the objectives of the Global Compact on Refugees, resettlement and complementary pathways.

The working paper makes a number of preliminary conclusions on the right of asylum in a regional perspective. With respect to *access to asylum*, all three regions contain an individual right to seek asylum broadly in line with the 1951 Convention. The Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR) is notable in establishing that, to ensure effectiveness, the asylum state owes a positive obligation to allow persons access to territory and asylum procedures.⁸

With respect to *asylum procedures*, the European asylum system has far more developed rules than the African and American systems. The Common European Asylum System (CEAS), in particular, includes sophisticated procedural guarantees related to the allocation of responsibility, asylum procedures and reception conditions. While both the IACtHR and the African Charter of Human and People's Rights (ACHPR) have developed procedural guarantees in their jurisprudence, these are not supported by detailed regional instruments.

In contrast, both the OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa (OAU Convention) and the Cartagena Declaration provide a broader *scope of international protection* than in Europe. The OAU Convention, notably, provides protection from conflict and indiscriminate violence in only part of the country of origin. The Cartagena Declaration, an influential soft law framework implemented through national legislation,

⁶ As set out in Article 38(1) of the Statute of the International Court of Justice. The Statute identifies three primary sources: international conventions, international custom, and general principles of law; and two secondary sources: judicial decisions and the teachings of pre-eminent jurists.

⁷ On this scholarly debate, see James C Hathaway, *Taking refugee rights seriously: A reply to Professor Hailbronner*, *VerfBlog*, available at <https://verfassungsblog.de/taking-refugee-rights-seriously-a-reply-to-professor-hailbronner/> accessed 25 March 2022; Gil-Bazo, María-Teresa. "Asylum as a general principle of international law." *International Journal of Refugee Law* 27.1 (2015): 3-28; Roman Boed, 'The state of the right of asylum in international law' (1994) 5 *Duke Journal of Comparative and International Law* 1.

⁸ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 122. See also *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 210.

expands the scope of protection by identifying five 'situational events' giving rise to refugeehood, based on objective conditions in the country of origin, such as generalised violence, internal conflict or massive violations of human rights. In contrast, the CEAS and European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) provide protection based on highly individualised procedures with a focus on protection from personal risk.

Regarding the content of international protection, the CEAS provides the most detailed set of standards for the treatment of refugees after status determination. The OAU Convention grants protection with respect to a number of key rights, including *non-refoulement*, temporary reception, non-discrimination, travel documents and the right to voluntary repatriation.⁹ The inter-American human rights system has aligned regional protection standards with those contained in the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol.

Finally, *resettlement and complementary pathways* within the three regions remain in the policy and not legal realm. Neither Africa nor the Americas currently have a dedicated regional mechanism, though Brazil led the regional Solidarity Resettlement Programme in operation between 2005 and 2014. Two *ad hoc* European Union (EU) resettlement schemes have been undertaken since 2015, in addition to the 2016 Proposal for a Regulation on a Union Resettlement Framework. However, the prospect of a legally binding European regional resettlement mechanism remains distant.

1.2 Aims

The aims of the working are

- To provide an overview of regional protection systems, with a focus on binding regional instruments in Europe, the Americas and Africa;
- To analyse the scope of key legal standards at the regional level, with specific reference to Brazil, Canada, South Africa and Turkey;
- To compare the normative scope of regional protection systems in Europe, the Americas and Africa.

1.3 Structure

This paper proceeds in five sections:

- First, the working paper provides an account of regional protection in Europe, encompassing both the Council of Europe and EU;

⁹ OAU Convention, art V.

- Second, regional protection in the Americas is addressed, with a focus on the inter-American human rights system and the Cartagena Declaration;
- Third, the working paper sets out the African regional protection system, drawing on the ACHPR and the OAU Convention;
- Fourth, regional soft law instruments in the Asia-Pacific and the Middle East are briefly addressed;
- Finally, the working paper concludes with some comparative findings on regional right of asylum.

2 THE RIGHT OF ASYLUM IN EUROPE

2.1 Introduction

Paragraph 5 of the GCR refers to several regional governance regimes as part of its legal foundation. One of them is the EU asylum *acquis*. Article 78 of the *Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union* (TFEU)¹⁰ and Article 18 of the *Charter on the Fundamental Rights of the European Union* (EUCFR)¹¹ form the legal foundation of the EU's regional refugee system. An elaborated system of secondary legislation, the CEAS, builds on these provisions¹² and the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) has developed far-reaching jurisprudence in this area.

Alongside the EU asylum *acquis*, Council of Europe standards of refugee protection derive from the regional human rights regime provided for in the *European Convention on Human Rights* (ECHR).¹³

¹⁰ Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union [2016] OJ C 202/1 (TFEU).

¹¹ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union [2012] OJ C 326/391 (EUCFR).

¹² See Directive 2013/32/EU of 26 June 2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection (recast) [2013] OJ L 180/60 (EU Asylum Procedures Directive, EUAPD); Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast) [2013] OJ L 180/96 (EU Reception Conditions Directive, EURCD); Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted (recast) [2011] OJ L 337/9 (EU Qualification Directive, EUQD); Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the member state responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the member states by a third-country national or a stateless person (recast) [2013] OJ L 180/31 (EU Dublin III); Regulation (EU) No 603/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on the establishment of 'Eurodac' for the comparison of fingerprints for the effective application of Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the Member States by a third-country national or a stateless person and on requests for the comparison with Eurodac data by Member States' law enforcement authorities and Europol for law enforcement purposes, and amending Regulation (EU) No 1077/2011 establishing a European Agency for the operational management of large-scale IT systems in the area of freedom, security and justice (recast) [2013] OJ L 180/1 (EURODAC Regulation).

¹³ European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14, adopted 4 November 1950, entry into force 3 September 1953, ETS No. 5 (ECHR); see further European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, adopted 26 November 1987, entry into force 1 March 2002, ETS No. 126.

While the EU has not acceded to the ECHR and is not yet a member to the Council of Europe,¹⁴ all EU Member States are individual members and thus bound by the ECHR. Furthermore, the Union explicitly recognises the ECHR's fundamental rights as general principles of EU law.¹⁵ The EUCFR and the ECHR both include clauses which safeguard the respective higher applicable human rights standard.¹⁶ The standards of international protection provided by the Refugee Convention is also integrated into the EU asylum *acquis* in both Article 78 TFEU and Article 18 EUCFR.

It is worth noting at this point that the expression “international protection” is used here in reference to the EU asylum *acquis*. International protection is defined according to Article 2(a) Qualification Directive (EUQD)¹⁷ as including “refugee status” within the meaning of the Refugee Convention as well as “subsidiary status”.¹⁸ This has been argued to narrow the meaning of “asylum” in the widest sense and misinterpreting the term “international protection”.¹⁹

Turkey, one of the six focus countries of the ASILE project, is not a Member State of the EU. However, there is a strong reciprocal influence between the jurisprudence of the CJEU and the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR).²⁰

¹⁴ Compare Consolidated version of the Treaty on European Union [2016] OJ C 202/1 (TEU), art 6(2); CJEU Opinion 2/13 [2014] ECLI:EU:C:2014:2454. Although the accession failed due to the CJEU Opinion in 2014, there is still a legal obligation for the EU to accede to the ECHR and negotiations have been resumed in 2020. Council of Europe, ‘EU Accession to the ECHR’ (*CDDH - System of the European Convention on Human Rights*) <<https://www.coe.int/en/web/human-rights-intergovernmental-cooperation/accession-of-the-european-union-to-the-european-convention-on-human-rights>> accessed 15 October 2021.

¹⁵ TEU, art 6(3).

¹⁶ See EUCFR arts 52, 53 and ECHR art 53.

¹⁷ Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted (recast) [2013] OJ L 337/9 (Qualification Directive, EUQD).

¹⁸ Compare EUQD, art 2(f): ‘person eligible for subsidiary protection’ means a third-country national or a stateless person who does not qualify as a refugee but in respect of whom substantial grounds have been shown for believing that the person concerned, if returned to his or her country of origin, or in the case of a stateless person, to his or her country of former habitual residence, would face a real risk of suffering serious harm as defined in Article 15, and to whom Article 17(1) and (2) does not apply, and is unable, or, owing to such risk, unwilling to avail himself or herself of the protection of that country;’.

¹⁹ See María-Teresa Gil-Bazo and Elspeth Guild, ‘The Right to Asylum’ in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (First Edition, Oxford University Press 2021) 867-882, 872.

²⁰ See eg Christiaan Timmermans, Will the accession of the EU to the European Convention on Human Rights fundamentally change the relationship between the Luxembourg and the Strasbourg Court? (EUI LAW, Centre for Judicial Cooperation DL, 2014) available at <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/31932> accessed 14 March 2022.

The latter is binding on Turkey as a party to the ECHR and member of the Council of Europe. Yet, Turkey has not ratified Protocol No. 4 to the European Convention of Human Rights, which prohibits collective expulsions of aliens.²¹

In addition, Turkey is party to the European Convention for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, the Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol. Turkey retains a geographical limitation obliging it to only provide Convention status to refugees from Europe, by declarations made under Article 1(B) of the Refugee Convention and its 1967 Protocol.²²

In September 2020, the European Commission presented a package of new proposals called the 'New Pact on Migration and Asylum'. It intends to be a 'fresh start to migration in Europe' and suggests several amendments to the European Common Asylum System based on 'building confidence through more effective procedures and striking a new balance between responsibility and solidarity.'²³ However, as the proposals are still being negotiated and their contents are not certain, this study will focus on the right of asylum in Europe as it currently stands.²⁴

2.2 Access to Asylum

Although neither the ECHR nor the EUCFR contains an explicit right to seek asylum, both hold protections regarding *non-refoulement*.²⁵ In particular,

²¹ Protocol No. 4 to the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, adopted 16 September 1963, entry into force 2 May 1968, ETS No. 46 (ECHR Protocol 4).

²² See further Nikolas Feith Tan and Jens Vedsted-Hansen, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards Refugee and Human Rights Law Standards Applicable to Asylum Governance* (ASILE, October 2021) available at <https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/D3.1-Catalogue-of-International-and-Regional-Legal-Standards-Final-draft.pdf> accessed 08 October 2021; Roberto Cortinovis, *Turkey – Country Note* (ASILE, April 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Country-Note_Turkey.pdf accessed 10 October 2021; Meltem Ineli-Ciger and Ozgenur Yigit, *Turkey - Country Fiche* (ASILE, October 2020) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_Turkey_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 10 October 2021.

²³ European Commission, 'Communication from the Commission on a New Pact on Migration and Asylum' COM (2020) 609 final, 23 September 2020. See 'New Pact on Migration and Asylum' (*European Commission*) <https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life/new-pact-migration-and-asylum_en> accessed 25 October 2021.

²⁴ For the connections between the Global Compact on Refugees and the EU's New Pact see Sergio Carrera and Andrew Geddes (eds), *The EU Pact on Migration and Asylum in Light of the United Nations Global Compact on Refugees: International Experiences on Containment and Mobility and Their Impacts on Trust and Rights* (European University Institute 2021).

²⁵ Both instruments are applicable to asylum applicants. According to Article 1 ECHR, everyone within the jurisdiction of Contracting Parties has the rights set out in Section I.

Article 3 ECHR, which prohibits torture and inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, implies a prohibition of *refoulement*. Based on this provision, a long line of ECtHR judgements has established the principle of *non-refoulement* as an exception to the sovereign right of states to control the entry, residence and expulsion of non-citizens.²⁶

Article 3 ECHR, which also binds Turkey, protects against any form of removal as ‘the question whether there is a real risk of treatment contrary to Article 3 in another state cannot depend on the legal basis for removal to that State.’²⁷ Instead, it engages the responsibility of the expelling State, where substantial grounds have been shown that the concerned individual would face a real risk of being subjected to treatment contrary to Article 3 in the receiving country.²⁸ Article 3 ECHR is further an absolute provision from which no derogation is possible in wartime or other national emergencies.²⁹ This makes it a particularly strong protection, going beyond the standard of Article 33 of the Refugee Convention.³⁰ Also regarding its scope of application, Article 3 ECHR forms a strong protection, since it has been interpreted to apply extraterritorially, *inter alia* on the high seas.³¹ Since not only reports of interceptions at sea, but also pushbacks at the EU’s external land borders have become frequent in the recent years, it is important to note that the border is included in the jurisdiction of Member States and Article 3 ECHR applies here too.³²

With respect to EU law, Article 18 EUCFR establishes a right to asylum ‘with due respect for the Geneva Convention of 28 July 1951 and the Protocol of 31

Article 51 EUCFR limits the application of the Charter for Member States to when they implement Union law.

²⁶ *Soering v The United Kingdom* App no 14038/88 (ECtHR, 7 July 1989); *Vilvarajah and Others v the United Kingdom* 45/1990/236/302-306 (ECtHR, 26 September 1991) para 102; and *Saadi v United Kingdom* App nos 13229/03 (ECtHR, 29 January 2008); see recently *M.D. and Others v Russia*, App no 71321/17 (ECtHR, 14 September 2019) para 90. Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (n 14) 23.

²⁷ *Babar Ahmed and Others v the United Kingdom* App nos 24027/07, 11949/08, 36742/08, 66911/09 and 67354/09 (ECtHR, 10 April 2012) para 168.

²⁸ *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v Italy* [GC] App no 27765/09 (ECtHR, 23 February 2012) para 114.

²⁹ *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v Italy* [GC] App no 27765/09 (ECtHR, 23 February 2012) para 129; *Al-Saadoon and Mufdhi v United Kingdom* App no 61498/08 (ECtHR, 2 March 2010) para 128; Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (n 14) 24.

³⁰ See Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (n 14) 15 ff on the limits of Article 33 of the 1951 Refugee Convention.

³¹ *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v Italy* [GC] App no 27765/09 (ECtHR, 23 February 2012) para 22; see further Seunghwan Kim, ‘Non-Refoulement and Extraterritorial Jurisdiction: State Sovereignty and Migration Controls at Sea in the European Context’ (2017) 30 *Leiden Journal of International Law* 49.

³² *Kebe and Others v Ukraine*, App no 12552/12 (ECtHR, 12 January 2017); *M.A. and Others v Lithuania*, App no 59793/17 (ECtHR, 11 December 2018); *M.K. and Others v Poland*, App nos 40503/17, 42902/17 and 43643/17 (ECtHR, 23 July 2020).

January 1967'. Article 19(2) EUCFR further codifies the principle of *non-refoulement* in the following terms:

No one may be removed, expelled or extradited to a State where there is a serious risk that he or she would be subjected to the death penalty, torture or other inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment.

Although the principle of *non-refoulement* derived from these provisions does not express a right to seek asylum, it holds great significance in this regard. To determine whether there is a risk of a violation of *non-refoulement*, each asylum application must be assessed.

The individual assessment of an asylum application is further guaranteed to a certain extent by the prohibition of collective expulsion according to Article 4 ECHR Protocol 4 and Article 19 (1) EUCFR.³³ However, neither are binding on Turkey. Therefore, the principle of *non-refoulement* as developed by the ECtHR jurisprudence on the basis of Article 3 ECHR is even more important in this context.³⁴

The EU asylum *acquis* further regulates access to asylum in secondary provisions. Article 4(3) of the EUQD and Article 10(3)(a) of the Asylum Procedures Directive (EUAPD)³⁵ oblige Member States to individually assess asylum applications. Article 6 EUAPD states that Member States must provide a system which gives applicants the possibility to lodge an application within few days of their arrival. In addition, Article 9 EUAPD grants the applicant a principal right to remain during the procedure.³⁶ Nevertheless, several Member States at the EU external borders engage in practices of deterrence, such as establishing transit zones, pushbacks and collective expulsion.³⁷

Another aspect to access to asylum is the right to leave a country. Article 2(2) ECHR Protocol 4 provides:

Everyone shall be free to leave any country, including his own.

³³ See recent confirmation of this notion by the ECtHR in *Shahzad v Hungary*, App no 12625/17 (ECtHR 8 July 2021) para 62; *D.A. and Others v Poland*, App no 51246/17 (ECtHR, 8 July 2021) para 66; *N.D. and N.T. v Spain* [GC] App nos 8675/15 and 8697/15 (ECtHR, 13 February 2020) para 198.

³⁴ *Ineli-Ciger and Yigit* (n 14).

³⁵ Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection [2013] OJ L 180/60 (Asylum Procedures Directive, EUAPD).

³⁶ See however APD, art 9 (2) for exceptions to this right.

³⁷ See recently *Shahzad v Hungary*, App no 12625/17 (ECtHR 8 July 2021); *D.A. and Others v Poland*, App no 51246/17 (ECtHR, 8 July 2021); *M.K. and Others v Poland*, App nos 40503/17, 42902/17 and 43643/17 (ECtHR 23 July 2020); *N.D. and N.T. v Spain* [GC] App nos 8675/15 and 8697/15 (ECtHR, 13 February 2020).

This right may, however, be subject to restrictions in accordance with law, which are 'necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security or public safety, for the maintenance of *ordre public*, for the prevention of crime, for the protection of health or morals, or for the protection of the rights and freedoms of others'³⁸ as well as to derogations according to Article 15 ECHR. The ECtHR jurisprudence on the right to leave in the context of asylum is limited. However, in *Xhavara and Others* the court did not find Article 2(2) ECHR applicable to measures intending to prevent the arrival of Albanians to Italy rather than preventing them to leave Albania.³⁹

2.3 Asylum Procedures

The need to establish asylum procedures for the determination of refugee status is presupposed, but not specifically regulated, by the Refugee Convention.⁴⁰ However, the principle of *non-refoulement* and the right to an effective remedy provided by Article 13 ECHR and Article 47 EUCFR require the assessment of individuals' asylum claims before deportation.⁴¹ The Council of Europe's Committee of Ministers issued non-binding recommendations on asylum procedures as early as in 1981.⁴² Now, there is a vast body of case law that provides procedural guarantees based on the rights to effective remedy, due process, fair trial and judicial protection.⁴³

Article 47 EUCFR states:

Everyone whose rights and freedoms guaranteed by the law of the Union are violated has the *right to an effective remedy* before a tribunal in compliance with the conditions laid down in this Article.

Everyone is entitled to a *fair and public hearing* within a reasonable time by an *independent and impartial tribunal* previously established by law.

³⁸ ECHR Protocol 4, art 2(3).

³⁹ *Xhavara and Others v Italy and Albania* App no 39473/98 (ECtHR, 11 January 2001) para 3; see already Tan and Vedsted-Hansen, Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards (n 14).

⁴⁰ Álvaro Botero and Jens Vedsted-Hansen, 'Asylum Procedure' in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (First Edition, Oxford University Press 2021) 589 with reference to Refugee Convention, arts 9 and 31.

⁴¹ See Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (n 14) 26 f.

⁴² Council of Europe, Committee of Ministers, Recommendation No R (81) 16 on the Harmonisation of National Procedures relating to Asylum, 5 November 1981; Recommendation No R (98) 13 on the right of rejected asylum seekers to an effective remedy against decisions on expulsion in the context of Art. 3 ECHR, 18 September 1998.

⁴³ See Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (n 14) 40 ff.

Everyone shall have the possibility of being *advised, defended and represented*.

Legal aid shall be made available to those who lack sufficient resources in so far as such aid is necessary to ensure effective access to justice.⁴⁴

Hence, the first paragraph of Article 47 EUCFR mirrors Article 13 ECHR holding the right to an 'an effective remedy before a national authority'.⁴⁵ The second paragraph resembles Article 6(1) ECHR, which provides:

In the determination of his *civil rights and obligations* or of any *criminal charge against him*, everyone is entitled to a fair and public hearing within a reasonable time by an independent and impartial tribunal established by law.⁴⁶

Although the ECtHR found that the right to a fair trial according to Article 6 (1) ECHR does not apply to procedures regarding entry, stay and deportation of aliens,⁴⁷ the protection from *refoulement* under Article 3 in connection with the right to an effective remedy under Article 13 ECHR provide the foundations for procedural guarantees of asylum applicants under the ECHR.⁴⁸ It is sufficient for the applicant to make an 'arguable claim' in order to fall within the scope of Article 3 in conjunction with Article 13 ECHR.⁴⁹ Furthermore, according to the ECtHR, asylum applicants must be informed of their right to apply for asylum to ensure their access to the procedure.⁵⁰ It must also be factually possible to submit an asylum application.⁵¹

2.3.1 Procedural rules in the EU asylum *acquis* & the ECHR

The EU asylum *acquis* regulates asylum procedures in detail through the EU Asylum Procedures Directive (EUAPD), complemented by the Qualification

⁴⁴ Emphasis added.

⁴⁵ ECHR, art 13.

⁴⁶ See further 'Handbook on European Law Relating to Asylum, Borders and Immigration. Edition 2020' (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights and Council of Europe) 147 <https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Handbook_asylum_ENG.pdf> accessed 21 October 2021.

⁴⁷ *Maaouia v France*, App no 39652/98 (ECtHR, 5 October 2000) 33 EHRR 42 para 40.

⁴⁸ See Tan and Vedsted-Hansen (n 14) 36 ff, 40 ff.

⁴⁹ See further *ibid* 41 with reference to *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011) para 288 and *M.K. and Others v Poland*, App nos 40503/17, 42902/17 and 43643/17 (ECtHR 23 July 2020) para 219.

⁵⁰ *Sharifi and Others v Italy and Greece*, App no 16643/09 (ECtHR, 21 October 2014) para 177 ff.

⁵¹ *A.E.A. v Greece*, App no 39034/12 (ECtHR, 15 March 2018) para 77; compare, however, *N.D. and N.T. v Spain* [GC] App nos 8675/15 and 8697/15 (ECtHR, 13 February 2020); see further Botero and Vedsted-Hansen (n 41) 599.

Directive (EUQD), the Return Directive (EURD) and, to some extent, the Dublin Regulation (Dublin III) as well as the Reception Conditions Directive (EURCD).⁵²

These instruments are focused on the individual case, as there is no established tradition of collective reception based on a group assessment.⁵³ As a result, instances of mass migration pose a great challenge for the EU Member States following this system.⁵⁴ The EU's special instrument to deal with such instances, the Temporary Protection Directive (EUTPD), was adopted in 2001 due to the experiences with mass displacement during the Yugoslavian armed conflicts. The EUTPD was never activated and, thus, declared "dead letter" until it was activated for the first time in response to the recent invasion of Ukraine. To the surprise of many legal scholars in Europe, this case of mass displacement caused the EU Member States to finally activate the EUTPD and receive Ukrainians on a group basis.⁵⁵

The EUAPD aims at establishing common procedures for the granting and withdrawing of international protection and, thereby, harmonising the national procedures within the EU.⁵⁶ It applies to asylum claims made in the territory of

⁵² Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals [2008] OJ L 348/98 (Return Directive, EURD); Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the Member State responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the Member States by a third-country national or a stateless person [2013] OJ L 180/31 (EU Dublin III); Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast) [2013] OJ L 180/96 (Reception Conditions Directive, EURCD). See further for mass influx situations Council Directive 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof [2001] OJ L 212/12 (EUTPD).

⁵³ See EUAPD, art 10 (3) (a) and EUQD, art 4 (3).

⁵⁴ Compare Tan and Vedsted-Hansen, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards* (n 14) 30 f.

⁵⁵ See eg Meltem İneli Cığır, '5 Reasons Why: Understanding the reasons behind the activation of the Temporary Protection Directive in 2022' (EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy Blog, 7 March 2022) available at <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/5-reasons-why-understanding-the-reasons-behind-the-activation-of-the-temporary-protection-directive-in-2022/> accessed 13 March 2022; Jessica Schultz et al, 'Collective protection as a short-term solution: European responses to the protection needs of refugees from the war in Ukraine' (EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy Blog, 7 March 2022) available at <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/collective-protection-as-a-short-term-solution-european-responses-to-the-protection-needs-of-refugees-from-the-war-in-ukraine/> accessed 13 March 2022.

⁵⁶ EUAPD, art 1; Evangelia (Lilian) Tsourdi, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Europe' in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (First Edition, Oxford University Press 2021) 358. This stands in strong connection with the establishment of the Schengen regime. Elaborating on this system would

EU Member States including at the border, the territorial waters and transit zones.⁵⁷

The EUQD regulates the personal scope of entitlement to international protection.⁵⁸ Regarding procedural rules, Article 4 EUQD requires the assessment of an asylum application to be carried out on an individual basis. It further sets out which elements must be assessed, including all relevant facts regarding the country of origin at the time of taking a decision, the individual circumstances of the applicant and their activities since leaving the country. It further gives rules on the assessment of evidence.⁵⁹

Chapter II of the EUAPD sets out the basic principles and guarantees for the asylum procedure within the EU. This includes the 'right to remain' during the procedure, requirements for the examination, such as individual, objective and impartial examinations, and for the decision, which must be given in writing, be reasoned and include information on remedies against a negative decision.⁶⁰ Article 12 EUAPD obliges Member States to give applicants information in a language they understand, access to interpretation and the opportunity to communicate with organisations providing legal advice.

According to Article 14 EUAPD, applicants must be given a personal interview, unless the authority can come to a positive decision on the basis of available evidence or unless the applicant is unfit or unable to be interviewed.⁶¹ The interview must take place without other family members present and in confidentiality, and it must allow the applicant to present their grounds in a comprehensive manner. The interviewer must be competent, should be of the same sex on the request of the applicant, must be accompanied by an interpreter and not wear military or law enforcement uniform. Interviews with minors must be conducted in a child-appropriate manner.⁶² A report of the interview must be made available to the applicant, who can make comments and provide clarification.⁶³ Article 18 EUAPD holds further safeguards regarding medical examinations.

exceed the scope of this study; see instead 'Handbook on European Law Relating to Asylum, Borders and Immigration. Edition 2020' (n 47) 32 ff.

⁵⁷ EUAPD, art 3 (1).

⁵⁸ See below in Chapter 3.4 on the Scope of International Protection in Europe.

⁵⁹ See EUQD, art 4.

⁶⁰ EUAPD, arts 10 and 11.

⁶¹ EUAPD, art 14 (2) (a) and (b).

⁶² EUAPD, art 15.

⁶³ EUAPD, art 17.

Member States shall ensure free legal assistance in the appeals procedures, unless there is 'no tangible prospect of success'.⁶⁴ In the first instance, this is limited to a right to information on certain aspects of the procedure.⁶⁵ At all stages of the procedures, asylum applicants have a right to legal counselling at their own cost.⁶⁶ The scope of legal advice is laid down in Article 23 EUAPD. Further guarantees concern special rules for vulnerable applicants, for unaccompanied minors, for detention, for withdrawal of the application and on the role of UNHCR.⁶⁷

The first-instance decision should be taken as soon as possible, without prejudice to an adequate and complete examination. The procedure should be concluded within six months of the lodging of the application.⁶⁸ Article 31(8) EUAPD lists certain circumstances that allow the procedure to be accelerated or conducted at the border or in transit zones, usually when there is some sort of misconduct or malice by the applicant or when the applicant is from a safe country of origin.

Article 33 EUAPD links the rules for asylum procedures to admissibility procedures under the Dublin III regulation.⁶⁹ In addition, it holds an exhaustive list of grounds for inadmissibility: international protection in another Member State, another first country of asylum, a safe third country or repeat applications. Apart from the latter case, a personal interview must still be conducted.⁷⁰

Under the EU asylum *acquis*, Article 46 EUAPD sets out the conditions and prerequisites for an effective remedy following Article 47 EUCFR. It requires a full and *ex nunc* examination of facts and law by a court or tribunal and includes a principal right to remain pending judicial review in the event of appeal. Furthermore, Member States must provide for reasonable time limits for the applicant to exercise the right.⁷¹

The many rules listed above do not apply to Turkey, which is not a Member State of the EU. However, similar – albeit less detailed – protections have been developed by the ECtHR in its case law. Next to access to procedures and information on the right to claim asylum, the Court has held that States have a

⁶⁴ EUAPD, art 20 (1) and (3); see further limitations in EUAPD, art 21.

⁶⁵ EUAPD, art 19, art 20 (2).

⁶⁶ EUAPD, art 22.

⁶⁷ EUAPD, arts 24-29.

⁶⁸ EUAPD, art 31. The procedure may be extended in certain cases, see EUAPD 31? (3-5).

⁶⁹ See section 2.3.2 on the Dublin Procedure below.

⁷⁰ EUAPD, arts 33, 34.

⁷¹ See EUAPD, art 46 (3)-(6).

positive obligation to examine the application within a reasonable time⁷² and that the procedure must remain confidential,⁷³ pursuant to Article 8 ECHR. There must be access to interpreters and legal aid as well as reliable communication between the authorities and the asylum seekers to guarantee an effective remedy.⁷⁴

Article 13 ECHR further requires independent and rigorous scrutiny by a national authority when substantial grounds exist that an expulsion holds a real risk of a violation of Article 2 or 3 ECHR.⁷⁵ There is also an obligation to identify special needs of applicants.⁷⁶ If minors are involved, the procedure must be conducted in line with the best interests of the child principle.⁷⁷ Acceleration of procedures is only permitted to a certain degree.⁷⁸ The burden of proof is shared, requiring that the applicant adduce evidence regarding personal circumstances, yet the difficulty to do so must be taken into account.⁷⁹ The ECtHR further requires the national remedy pursuant to Article 13 ECHR in conjunction with Article 2 or 3 ECHR to have automatic suspensive effect due to the potential irreversible harm.⁸⁰

2.3.2 Dublin Procedure

The EU has an elaborated system of responsibility-sharing that is based on the possibility in international refugee law to provide for refugees' 'protection

⁷² *B.A.C. v Greece*, App no 11981/15 (ECtHR, 13 October 2016) 39; *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011) para 262; with regard to detention see *Abdolkhani and Karimnia v Turkey*, App no 30471/08 (ECtHR, 22 September 2009) para 139.

⁷³ *X v Sweden*, App no 36417/16 (ECtHR 9 January 2018) para 47.

⁷⁴ *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011) para 301; see further *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v Italy*, App no 27765/09 (ECtHR, 23 February 2012) para 202; *Saadi v Italy* [GC] App no 37201/06 (ECtHR, 28 February 2008) para 52.

⁷⁵ *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011) para 293.

⁷⁶ See eg *OM v Hungary*, App no 9912/15 (ECtHR, 5 July 2016) para 53.

⁷⁷ *Tarakhel v Switzerland*, App no 29217/12 (ECtHR, 4 November 2014); see Convention on the Rights of the Child (adopted 20 November 1989, entered into force 2 September 1990) 1577 UNTS 3. The best interest of the child is also incorporated in the EUAPD through many special provisions taking the special position of minors and, in particular, unaccompanied minors into account; compare EUAPD, art 25.

⁷⁸ *IM v France*, App no 9152/09 (ECtHR, 2 February 2012) para 144.

⁷⁹ *JK and Others v Sweden* [GC] App no 59166/12 (ECtHR, 28 August 2016) para 91 f. See in detail Botero and Vedsted-Hansen (n 41) 599 ff.

⁸⁰ *Hirsi Jamaa and Others v Italy* [GC] App no 27765/09 (ECtHR, 23 February 2012) paras 197 ff; *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011) para 293 with references to previous ECtHR case-law; *Gebremedhin v France*, App no 25389/05 (ECtHR, 26 April 2007).

elsewhere'.⁸¹ This system is regulated by the Dublin Regulation,⁸² which has been revised two times, but continues to receive strong critique from scholars.⁸³ A frequent misconception is that the primary aim of this system was the achievement of a fair burden-sharing mechanism based on solidarity of the EU Member States. Instead, the Dublin system forms an intrinsic part of the Schengen area as well as the Area of Freedom, Security and Justice within the EU and is thus designed to prevent forum-shopping with the control of the external EU borders in mind.⁸⁴

The Dublin Regulation also ensures access to asylum procedures, as it requires EU Member States to examine any application for international protection lodged by a third-country national or a stateless person on the territory, including borders and transit zones. This application must be examined by one single Member State.⁸⁵ The responsible Member State is determined on the criteria established by Chapter III of the Regulation, which assumes some connection to the Member State, such as family connections or first country of arrival.⁸⁶

The Regulation further establishes procedures for the transfer to the responsible State. Member States can request each other to take back or take charge of applicants within defined time frames and regarding certain evidence.⁸⁷ Within its scope of application, the Regulation provides for certain

⁸¹ James C Hathaway, 'The Michigan Guidelines on Protection Elsewhere' (2007) 28 *The Michigan Journal of International Law* 207; see further Michelle Foster, 'Protection Elsewhere: The Legal Implications of Requiring Refugees to Seek Protection in Another State' (2007) 28 *Michigan Journal of International Law*.

⁸² Regulation (EU) No 604/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 establishing the criteria and mechanisms for determining the member state responsible for examining an application for international protection lodged in one of the member states by a third-country national or a stateless person (recast) [2013] OJ L 180/31 (Dublin III Regulation).

⁸³ See amongst many Ashley Binetti Armstrong, 'You Shall Not Pass: How the Dublin System Fueled Fortress Europe' (2019) 20 *Chicago Journal of International Law* 332, 349 ff; Constantin Hruschka, 'Dublin Is Dead! Long Live Dublin! The 4 May 2016 Proposal of the European Commission – EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy' (*EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy*) <<http://eumigrationlawblog.eu/dublin-is-dead-long-live-dublin-the-4-may-2016-proposal-of-the-european-commission/>> accessed 24 October 2021; Francesco Maiani, 'The Reform of the Dublin III Regulation' (European Parliament, Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs 2016) <[http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/571360/IPOL_STU\(2016\)571360_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2016/571360/IPOL_STU(2016)571360_EN.pdf)> accessed 24 October 2021.

⁸⁴ See Schengen Borders Code, TFEU, Title V.

⁸⁵ Dublin III, art 3 (1).

⁸⁶ Dublin III, arts 7 ff.

⁸⁷ Dublin III, arts 21 ff.

guarantees for minors,⁸⁸ a right to information of the individual,⁸⁹ a right to effective remedy⁹⁰ and for the confidentiality of personal information.⁹¹

In addition, the Dublin system is founded on a presumption between EU Member States that asylum applicants receive respect for their fundamental rights throughout the EU and, hence, that other EU Member States are 'safe countries'. As the CJEU has repeatedly demonstrated, this is not guaranteed.⁹²

2.3.3 Return Procedures

The EU asylum *acquis* provides further procedural safeguards in the Return Directive (EURD).⁹³ Article 5 safeguards the principle of *non-refoulement*, the best interests of the child, family life and health during the implementation of the EURD. Article 7 EURD further gives preference to voluntary departure instead of forced removals and Article 9 EURD provides for postponement in case of a breach of *non-refoulement*, suspensive effect of a remedy, the individual's health or technical reasons.

According to Article 12 EURD, decisions must be reasoned, in writing and include information on remedies, principally in a language that the person understands.⁹⁴ Article 13 EURD sets out the right to an effective remedy before a judicial or administrative authority or an independent and impartial body competent to suspend removal temporarily pending the review.⁹⁵ Article 14 EURD provides principles to be taken into account during the period for voluntary departure or while the removal has been postponed, including for

⁸⁸ Dublin III, art 6.

⁸⁹ Dublin III, art 4, 26

⁹⁰ Dublin III, art 27; see eg CJEU Case C-63/15 *Mehrdad Ghezelbash v. Staatssecretaris van Veiligheid en Justitie* [2016] ECLI:EU:C:2016:409.

⁹¹ Dublin III, art 39.

⁹² CJEU Joined Cases C-411/10 and C-493/10, *N.S. v. Secretary of State for the Home Department and M.E. and Others v. Refugee Applications Commissioner & Minister for Justice, Equality and Law Reform* [2011] ECLI:EU:C:2011:865 para 94 stating that Member States '(...) may not transfer an asylum seeker to the 'Member State responsible' within the meaning of Regulation No 343/2003 where they cannot be unaware that systemic deficiencies in the asylum procedure and in the reception conditions of asylum seekers in that Member State amount to substantial grounds for believing that the asylum seeker would face a real risk of being subjected to inhuman or degrading treatment within the meaning of Article 4 of the Charter.'; compare prior ECtHR judgment regarding Greece in *M.S.S. v Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011); see further regarding Italy CJEU Case C-163/17 *Abubacarr Jawo v. Bundesrepublik Deutschland* ECLI:EU:C:2019:218; regarding medical treatment CJEU Case C-578/16 *C.K. and Others v. Slovenia* ECLI:EU:C:2017:127.

⁹³ Directive 2008/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on common standards and procedures in Member States for returning illegally staying third-country nationals [2008] OJ L 348/98 (Return Directive, EURD).

⁹⁴ EURD, art 12 (3) for exceptions.

⁹⁵ See eg CJEU Joined Cases C-924/19 PPU and C-925/19 PPU PPU *FMS and Others* EU:C:2020:367.

families, illness, minors or other vulnerable persons. Articles 15 ff EURD clarify the circumstances for detention pending removal.

The ECtHR provides for similar safeguards in its case law pursuant to Article 13 ECHR and Article 1 of ECHR Protocol No 7 for the expulsion of 'lawfully residing aliens', as well as Article 8 ECHR. The latter is often relevant for persons who have remained in a country for an extended period of time pending their procedure and, in this time, have developed family or other personal ties in the respective country.

2.4 The Scope of International Protection

The EUQD definition of refugee status is largely based on the Refugee Convention. Article 2 (d) EUQD states:

'refugee' means a third-country national who, owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, political opinion or membership of a particular social group, is outside the country of nationality and is unable or, owing to such fear, is unwilling to avail himself or herself of the protection of that country, or a stateless person, who, being outside of the country of former habitual residence for the same reasons as mentioned above, is unable or, owing to such fear, unwilling to return to it, and to whom Article 12 does not apply;

The EUQD is more detailed than the Refugee Convention on the rules for refugee status recognition and explicitly recognises refugees *sur place*⁹⁶ and persecution by non-state actors.⁹⁷ What stands out is that, building on Article 1(A) of the Refugee Convention, Article 9(1)(a) EUQD attempts a definition of 'persecution' as an act that is:

sufficiently serious by its nature or repetition as to constitute a severe violation of basic human rights, in particular the rights from which derogation cannot be made under Article 15(2) of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms;⁹⁸

International scholars have interpreted the Refugee Convention's meaning of persecution going beyond the violation of basic human rights and, for this reason, view the EUQD's definition critically.⁹⁹ However, the provision cannot

⁹⁶ EUQD, art 5.

⁹⁷ EUQD, art 6.

⁹⁸ EUQD, art 9 (1) (a).

⁹⁹ See James C Hathaway and Michelle Foster, *The Law of Refugee Status* (Second edition, Cambridge University Press 2014) 202 ff; see further Harald Dörig, 'Asylum Qualification Directive 2011/95/EU, Articles 1-10' in Kay Hailbronner and Daniel Thym (eds), *EU*

be read as limited to non-derogable rights under Articles 2, 3, 4(1) and 7 ECHR, but highlights the right to life as well as the prohibition of torture, of slavery and of unlawful punishment as 'basic human rights'. Paragraph (b) further recognises that an accumulation of various measures, including the violation of human rights, can reach the same level of severity as an act according to Paragraph (a). The CJEU has ruled that interference with religious freedom 'may be so serious as to be treated in the same way as the cases referred to in Article 15(2) of the ECHR'.¹⁰⁰ Hence, the threshold is that of sufficient seriousness rather than the violation of specific rights¹⁰¹ and the severity must be viewed in the light of personal circumstances according to Article 4(3) EUQD.

Article 9(2) EUQD includes a demonstrative list of acts that may rise to the level of persecution, such as physical or mental violence, discriminatory legal measures, disproportionate or discriminatory punishment, prosecution for refusal of military service, gender- or child-specific acts.¹⁰² According to Article 9(3) EUQD, there must be a nexus between the acts of persecution (or the absence of protection) and the reasons listed in Article 10 EUQD. Article 10 EUQD continues by defining the reasons for persecution in accordance with Article 1(A)(2) of the Refugee Convention – the grounds of race, religion, nationality, a particular social group and political opinion. Article 10 (2) EUQD further clarifies that it is 'immaterial whether the applicant actually possesses the racial, religious, national, social or political characteristic' as long as the persecutor attributes it to the applicant.

Another issue of note with respect to the scope of protection under the EU asylum *acquis* is the EUQD's definition of 'particular social group'. Article 10(1)(d) provides:

[A] group shall be considered to form a particular social group where *in particular*:

- members of that group share an innate characteristic, or a common background that cannot be changed, or share a characteristic or

Immigration and Asylum Law (CH Beck, Hart, Nomos 2022) Art 9 MN 4 for an overview of scholarship on the definition of persecution in international law.

¹⁰⁰ CJEU Joined Cases C-71/11 and C-99/11, *Bundesrepublik Deutschland v Y and Z*, ECLI:EU:C:2012:518 para 57; see further CJEU Joined Cases C-199/12, C-200/12 and C-201/12, *X, Y and Z*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:720 para 54 ff.

¹⁰¹ See further International Association of Refugee Law Judges European Chapter (IARLJ Europe), *Qualification for International Protection (Directive 2011/95/EU): A Judicial Analysis* (EASO 2016) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2847/52563>> accessed 26 October 2021; Dörig (n 100) Art 9.

¹⁰² See in detail EUQD, art 9 (2); see further CJEU Case C-56/17 *Bahtiyar Fathi v Predsedatel na Darzhavna agentsia za bezhantsite*, ECLI:EU:C:2018:803; C-56/17 CJEU Case C-472/13, *Andre Lawrence Shepherd v Bundesrepublik Deutschland*, ECLI:EU:C:2015:117.

belief that is so fundamental to identity or conscience that a person should not be forced to renounce it, *and*

- that group has a distinct identity in the relevant country, because it is perceived as being different by the surrounding society.¹⁰³

Although the wording ‘in particular’ implies a non-exhaustive definition, the CJEU interpreted these two elements to apply cumulatively in *X, Y and Z*, hence, narrowing the protection scope compared to the Refugee Convention.¹⁰⁴ The EUQD’s definition of particular social group has further been criticised for holding that ‘[s]exual orientation cannot be understood to include acts considered to be criminal in accordance with national law of the Member States’,¹⁰⁵ since the criminalization of sexual orientation can itself constitute persecution.¹⁰⁶

In addition to refugee status, the EUQD includes ‘subsidiary protection’ status,¹⁰⁷ which shall be granted if the person would face a real risk of suffering serious harm, defined in Article 15 as:

- (a) the death penalty or execution; or
- (b) torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment of an applicant in the country of origin; or
- (c) serious and individual threat to a civilian’s life or person by reason of indiscriminate violence in situations of international or internal armed conflict.¹⁰⁸

Since the ECHR does not include a right to asylum, no specific rules for refugee status recognition exist beyond the principle of *non-refoulement* developed in the ECtHR case law. This means that in Turkey the scope of international protection is largely a matter of national law.¹⁰⁹

2.5 The Content of International Protection

Chapter VII of the EUQD sets out the content of international protection for beneficiaries of international protection, i.e. refugees and persons eligible for

¹⁰³ Emphasis added.

¹⁰⁴ CJEU Joined Cases C-199/12, C-200/12 and C-201/12, *X, Y and Z*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:720 para 45; see further Hathaway and Foster (n 100) 429 f.

¹⁰⁵ EUQD, art 10 (1) (d).

¹⁰⁶ Hathaway and Foster (n 100) 445.

¹⁰⁷ EUQD, art 2 (f).

¹⁰⁸ EUQD, art 15.

¹⁰⁹ See Cortinovis (n 14); Ineli-Ciger and Yigit (n 14).

subsidiary protection, in the EU Member States.¹¹⁰ The EUQD does not preclude any rights laid down in the Refugee Convention and recognises the declaratory nature of the determination of refugee status.¹¹¹ Subsequently, Chapter VII includes a list of positive obligations for Member States, including protection from *refoulement*, information on rights and obligations, the maintenance of family unity, the issuance of residence permits and travel documents, granting access to employment, to education, to recognition of qualifications, to social welfare and healthcare, to accommodation, to freedom of movement within the territory and to integration facilities.¹¹² In addition, Article 31 EUQD holds special obligations towards unaccompanied minors.

Most of these obligations are only applicable after successful determination of refugee or subsidiary protection status. Some of them also distinguish between refugee status under the Refugee Convention and subsidiary protection, such as the right to social welfare, which may be limited towards persons receiving the latter.¹¹³ Furthermore, the rights must be granted on the same level as for nationals or other legal residents.¹¹⁴ Therefore, the difference between the levels of social rights amongst the Member States has, amongst other reasons, led to the fear that asylum applicants prefer to lodge applicants in wealthier states.¹¹⁵ Consequently, many EU Member States try to limit the access to social rights for beneficiaries of international protection.

Unlike the Refugee Convention, which grants rights according to several 'levels of attachment' to the asylum state,¹¹⁶ the EU CEAS makes a clear distinction by providing rights and obligations towards recognised beneficiaries of international protection in the EUQD and towards applicants for international protection in the EURCD.

The EURCD provides minimum standards, but Member States may introduce more favourable provisions.¹¹⁷ Within three days of lodging an asylum application, Member States must issue a document providing the name of the person and the status as asylum applicant, which is important to show that the

¹¹⁰ See EUQD art 20 (1) and (2).

¹¹¹ See EUQD art 20 (1) and recital 21; compare Tan and Vedsted-Hansen, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards* (n 14) 27.

¹¹² See EUQD, arts 20-34.

¹¹³ EUQD, art 29 (2).

¹¹⁴ See EUQD, arts 21 ff.

¹¹⁵ See eg Daniel Thym, 'Secondary Movements: Overcoming the Lack of Trust among the Member States?' (*EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy*, 29 October 2020) <<https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/secondary-movements-overcoming-the-lack-of-trust-among-the-member-states/>> accessed 17 October 2021.

¹¹⁶ See James C Hathaway, *The Rights of Refugees under International Law* (2nd edn, Cambridge University Press 2021) 173 ff.

¹¹⁷ EURCD, art 4.

person has a right to remain and receive access to other benefits under the EURCD.¹¹⁸ Within 15 days of lodging an asylum application, asylum applicants must be informed of the benefits and obligations, particularly on organisations that provide legal or other assistance.¹¹⁹

Within three months, minors should receive access to the education system.¹²⁰ Applicants should have effective access to the labour market¹²¹ within nine months and access to vocational training. Furthermore, Article 17(2) EURCD states:

Member States shall ensure that material reception conditions provide *an adequate standard of living* for applicants, which guarantees their subsistence and protects their physical and mental health.¹²²

What an adequate standard of living includes is subject to discussion and strongly varies in the respective Member States.¹²³ Both the CJEU and the ECtHR have determined that systemic flaws in the reception conditions have resulted in inhuman and degrading treatment in violation of Article 4 EUCFR and Article 3 ECHR.¹²⁴ Under EU law, a failure to provide adequate living conditions can give rise to so-called *Francovich* damages, by which a Member State may be liable to compensate individuals for damages caused by the Member State's failure to transpose an EU directive into national law.¹²⁵

2.6 Resettlement and complementary pathways

One objective of the GCR is the expansion of 'third country solutions', defined in the Compact as 'resettlement and complementary pathways to admission'.¹²⁶ At present, there is no binding EU mechanism for the protection

¹¹⁸ EURCD, art 6 (1); see further exceptions in EURCD, art 6 (2).

¹¹⁹ EURCD, art 5 (1).

¹²⁰ EURCD, art 14.

¹²¹ EURCD, art 15.

¹²² Emphasis added.

¹²³ Lilian Tsourdi, 'Asylum Reception Conditions Directive 2013/33/EU' in Kay Hailbronner and Daniel Thym (eds), *EU Immigration and Asylum Law* (CH Beck, Hart, Nomos 2022) art 17 MN 9 ff with further references. See modalities for housing in EURCD, art 18 (1) and for health care in EURCD, art 19.

¹²⁴ CJEU Joined Cases C-411/10 and C-493/10, *N. S. and M. E.*, ECLI:EU:C:2011:865; *N.H. and Others v France*, App nos 28820/13, 75547/13 and 13114/15 (ECtHR, 2 July 2020); *M.S.S. v. Belgium and Greece* [GC] App no 30696/09 (ECtHR, 21 January 2011).

¹²⁵ 'Handbook on European Law Relating to Asylum, Borders and Immigration. Edition 2020' (n 47) 159 with reference to CJEU Joined Cases C-6 and 9/90, *Francovich and Bonifaci v Republic of Italy* [1991] ECR I-5403.

¹²⁶ The GCR identifies complementary pathways as comprising family reunification, private refugee sponsorship, humanitarian visas and labour and educational opportunities for refugees. GCR, paras 7 and 95. UNHCR defines them as 'safe and regulated avenues for

of refugees via resettlement or complementary pathways. Two *ad hoc* EU resettlement schemes have been undertaken since 2015. In the first, 19,452 refugees were resettled to the EU between 2015 and 2017. In the second, 50,000 refugees were resettled between 2018 and 2020. Between January 2020 and June 2021, EU Member States resettled approximately 13,500 refugees as the COVID-19 pandemic slowed resettlement globally.¹²⁷

In addition, EU-Turkey arrangements have expanded humanitarian admission programmes to the EU.¹²⁸ Notably, following the EU-Turkey Statement,¹²⁹ Germany established a Humanitarian Admission Program (HAP) with Turkey. Under this programme, 13,694 places originally planned for intra-EU relocation were reassigned to HAP Turkey.¹³⁰

In 2016, the EU Commission put forward a Proposal for a Regulation on a Union Resettlement Framework. It emphasises the importance of a stable framework for sustainable and predictable resettlement frameworks for the Union, with a complementary role for humanitarian admission programmes.¹³¹ The Proposal for a Union Resettlement Framework aims to ensure coherence throughout the EU, to reduce the risk of mass influx, to achieve foreign policy objectives, to show a sign of solidarity and to provide legal and safe pathways for persons in need of international protection.

The Proposal includes rules on eligibility and exclusion, common procedures, the status to be accorded and financial support to the Member States. The concrete implementation relies on the Council and the Commission to adopt annual resettlement plans.¹³² These plans determine *inter alia* the number of

refugees that complement resettlement by providing lawful stay in a third country where their international protection needs are met.' UNHCR, *Complementary Pathways for Admission of Refugees to Third Countries: Key considerations*, 2019) 5.

¹²⁷ European Commission, Report on Migration and Asylum COM (2021) 590 final, 29 September 2021, 21.

¹²⁸ On EU-Turkey arrangements, see Nikolas Feith Tan and Jens Vedsted-Hansen, *Inventory and Typology of EU Arrangements with Third Countries: Instruments and Actors*, 2021); Ineli-Ciger and Yigit (n 14).

¹²⁹ European Council, 'EU-Turkey Statement (Press Release)' (*European Council - Council of the European Union*, 18 March 2016) <<http://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2016/03/18/eu-turkey-statement/>> accessed 29 November 2021.

¹³⁰ Pauline Endres de Oliveira, 'Humanitarian Admission to Germany—Access vs. Rights?' in Marie-Claire Foblets and Luc Leboeuf (eds), *Humanitarian Admission to Europe* (Humanitarian Admission to Europe, Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft mbH & Co. KG 2020) 206.

¹³¹ See Commission Recommendation (EU) 2020/1364 of 23 September 2020 on legal pathways to protection in the EU: promoting resettlement, humanitarian admission and other complementary pathways [2020] OJ L 317/13, recitals 12, 24.

¹³² European Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union Resettlement Framework and amending Regulation (EU) No 516/2014 of the European Parliament and the Council' COM (2016) 468 final.

persons who should be resettled and from which countries or regions depending on various factors. One of the factors is how well the countries cooperate with the EU, hence, instrumentalising resettlement for foreign policy – a suggestion that has been criticised for neglecting the humanitarian purpose of resettlement.¹³³

This issue has been a particular sensitive one in European (as well as in the global) asylum policy. Although consensus exists that there must be a fair sharing of responsibility, the views on what is 'fair' differ widely. Some Member States do not intend to agree to any binding rules on what they see as an area of sovereign power, while some on principle do not wish to receive any further asylum applicants on their territory. For this reason, progress on the adoption of the Union Resettlement Framework can be expected to be slow.

2.7 Conclusions

In sum, EU law as well as the ECHR incorporate the protection guarantees of the Refugee Convention in the legal provisions and the corresponding case law. On the one hand, the ECtHR relies mostly on regional human rights provisions guaranteeing the protection of life, the prohibition of torture, the right to family life and to an effective remedy in order to develop a system of refugee protection in its case law.

On the other hand, the EU asylum *acquis* provides elaborate rules on all procedural and substantive conditions for the guarantee of international protection. By doing so, it increases clarity and legal certainty for the individuals concerned as well as for Member States. It further attempts to provide a harmonised system throughout the region. In addition, the EU asylum *acquis* is backed by the protections of fundamental rights according to the EUCFR and the case law of the CJEU.

Hence, the detailed and binding legal provisions and the supervision of States by two powerful regional courts make for a comparatively strong system of regional standards for refugee protection in Europe.

A disadvantage of this narrow net of rules is that some dimensions of the rights developed from the Refugee Convention cannot take place within the correct interpretation of the CEAS rules. By providing detailed legal provisions for certain circumstances, it is made clear that other circumstances are excluded.

¹³³ See Luc Leboeuf, 'Legal Pathways to Protection: Towards a Common and Comprehensive Approach?' (*EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy*, 3 December 2020) <<https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/legal-pathways-to-protection-towards-a-common-and-comprehensive-approach/>> accessed 1 November 2021 with further references.

For instance, the explicit description of a 'particular social group' overhauls the approaches developed in the interpretation of the Refugee Convention. And by providing a system for subsidiary protection under the scope of international protection in the case of indiscriminate violence, the provisions show that the scope is not covering persons displaced by disaster.

Furthermore, by providing such a narrow net of rules, the system has turned out to be too inflexible to adapt to a sudden change of circumstances. This was the case, for example, in autumn 2015 when the number of asylum applications in Europe increased sharply within a short period of time. Many of the persons arrived by land or boat via the EU Member States at the external borders. According to the Dublin system, their asylum applications should have been registered after the first contact with national authorities in these 'countries of first arrival'. Due to the increase in numbers and the administrative burden necessary to conduct proper registrations and initial interviews in accordance with the procedural provisions, the national authorities were overwhelmed. Hence, many Member States simply resorted to assisting the irregular arrivals in their transit through Europe.

3 THE RIGHT OF ASYLUM IN THE AMERICAS

3.1 Introduction

Three primary regional instruments govern the right of asylum in the Americas. Covering the whole region, the *1948 American Declaration on the Rights and Duties of Man* (ADHR) sets out the region's 'first set of comprehensive international standards in relation to human rights and duties.'¹³⁴ While the ADHR is formally non-binding, some authors consider the Declaration binding on Member States of the Organization of American States (OAS) as the codification of regional practice.¹³⁵

The second primary regional instrument is the *Organization of American States Charter* (OAS Charter), which created the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights (IACHR). The IACHR is a source of non-binding guidance in the Inter-American human rights system.¹³⁶ In turn, the *1969 American Convention on Human Rights* (ACHR) created the IACtHR, which produces binding jurisprudence upon referral from the Commission.¹³⁷

Both Brazil and Canada are party to the ADHR and OAS Charter and thus recognise the function of the IACHR. On the other hand, while Brazil is a party to the ACHR and has recognised the jurisdiction of the IACtHR since 1998,¹³⁸ Canada has not ratified the ACHR and does not recognise the jurisdiction of the Court.¹³⁹

Both the Court and Commission have developed jurisprudence on the rights of asylum seekers and refugees, with the Commission being particularly active through its individual petitions mechanism. According to Cantor and Barichello,

¹³⁴ David James Cantor and Stefania Barichello, 'Protection of Asylum Seekers under the Inter-American Human Rights System', *Regional Approaches to the Protection of Asylum Seekers* (Regional Approaches to the Protection of Asylum Seekers, Routledge 2016).

¹³⁵ Ibid 5, 36. For a contrary view, see Jose H Fischel de Andrade, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Latin America', in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam, *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (Oxford University Press 2021) 324.

¹³⁶ Jose H Fischel de Andrade, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Latin America', in Costello, Foster and McAdam, *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law*

¹³⁷ Joel Hernández, 'Inter-American standards on migration, asylum and refugee law' (2018) 2 *University of Vienna Law Review* 198; David James Cantor and Stefania Eugenia Barichello, 'The Inter-American human rights system: a new model for integrating refugee and complementary protection?' (2013) 17 *The International Journal of Human Rights* 689.

¹³⁸ Roberto Cortinovia & Lorenzo Rorro, Country Note BRAZIL (ASILE Country Note, April 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Country-Note_Brazil.pdf accessed 22 September 2021 2.

¹³⁹ Roberto Cortinovia, Country Note CANADA (ASILE Country Note, April 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Country-Note_Canada.pdf accessed 22 September 2021 2.

jurisprudence, such as the well-known *Haitian Interdictions* case, has focused on North American respondents, likely due to their status as destination states and active strategic litigation programmes.¹⁴⁰

At the sub-regional level, *1984 Cartagena Declaration on Refugees* is a highly influential soft law framework that has increased the scope of protection for refugees through uptake in national legislation, including in Brazil.¹⁴¹ Initially adopted by 10 regional governments, the Cartagena Declaration expands the definition of 'refugee' contained in the 1951 Refugee Convention by extending it to persons fleeing 'generalized violence, foreign aggression, internal conflicts, massive violation of human rights or other circumstances which have seriously disturbed public order'.¹⁴²

Regional initiatives have followed the Cartagena Declaration every ten years.¹⁴³ The *1994 San Jose Declaration* reiterated the 'overriding importance' of the Cartagena framework and put forward a number of principles on internal displacement in the region.¹⁴⁴

The *2004 Mexico Declaration* affirmed the commitment of Latin American states to keep their borders open to guarantee the protection and security of those in need of international protection. Operationally, the 2004 Mexico Declaration included a Plan of Action for the first time, comprising three programmes: Borders of Solidarity; Cities of Solidarity; and the Brazil-led Solidarity Resettlement Programme.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴⁰ Cantor and Barichello, 'Protection of Asylum Seekers under the Inter-American Human Rights System'.

¹⁴¹ UNHCR, *Summary Conclusions on the interpretation of the extended refugee definition in the 1984 Cartagena Declaration; roundtable 15 and 16 October 2013, Montevideo, Uruguay*, 7 July 2014. On asylum governance in Brazil, see Natália Medina Araújo, Brazil - Country Fiche (January 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_BRAZIL_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 16 August 2021.

¹⁴² Colloquium on the International Protection of Refugees in Central America, Mexico and Panama. *Cartagena Declaration on Refugees*. Cartagena de Indias, 22 November 1984. For a critical account of the Declaration's development, see José H Fischel de Andrade, "The 1984 Cartagena Declaration: A Critical Review of Some Aspects of Its Emergence and Relevance." *Refugee Survey Quarterly* 38.4 (2019): 341-362.

¹⁴³ Gilberto M. A. Rodrigues, South America and the Cartagena Regime: a comprehensive approach to forced migration responses, ASILE Forum, 10 November 2020, available at <https://www.asileproject.eu/south-america-and-the-cartagena-regime/> accessed 16 August 2021.

¹⁴⁴ San José Declaration on Refugees and Displaced Persons, 7 December 1994, available at <https://www.refworld.org/docid/4a54bc3fd.html> accessed 23 September 2021.

¹⁴⁵ Carlos Maldonado Castillo, "The Cartagena process: 30 years of innovation and solidarity." *Forced Migration Review* 49 (2015): 89.

Most recently, in December 2014, the *Brazil Declaration and Plan of Action* was agreed upon with the aim of strengthening national bodies for the determination of refugee status, including at border areas.¹⁴⁶ The Plan of Action includes 11 programmes, including the eradication of statelessness, labour mobility pathways and a focus on displacement caused by organised crime.¹⁴⁷ The *Brazil Declaration and Plan of Action* further includes programmes focused on two sub-regions, the Northern Triangle countries of Central America and the Caribbean.¹⁴⁸

Brazil incorporated elements of the Cartagena Declaration definition into its national legislation in 1992, albeit in a fairly circumscribed way, and has signed on to all four subsequent initiatives. Following the 1994 *San Jose Declaration*, Brazil's Refugee Law 9.474 of 1997 incorporated the Refugee Convention definition and, as an additional incorporation of the Cartagena Declaration, recognises that protection is due to any individual that 'due to gross and generalized violations of human rights is forced to leave his/her country of nationality to seek refuge in another country'.¹⁴⁹

3.2 Access to Asylum

Both the ADHR and ACHR provide for an explicit right to seek and receive asylum. Article XXVII of the ADHR, which predates the Universal Declaration of Human Rights by eight months, provides:

¹⁴⁶ Mexico Declaration and Plan of Action to Strengthen the International Protection of Refugees in Latin America. Mexico City, 16 November 2004; Brazil Declaration: A Framework for Cooperation and Regional Solidarity to Strengthen the International Protection of Refugees, Displaced and Stateless Persons in Latin America and the Caribbean. Brasilia, 3 December 2014. See further Roberto Cortinovis & Lorenzo Rorro, Country Note BRAZIL (ASILE Country Note, April 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Country-Note_Brazil.pdf accessed 16 August 2021.

¹⁴⁷ Carlos Maldonado Castillo, "The Cartagena process: 30 years of innovation and solidarity." *Forced Migration Review* 49 (2015): 89.

¹⁴⁸ David James Cantor, "Cooperation on refugees in Latin America and the Caribbean." Elena Fiddian-Qasmiyeh and Patricia O. Daley (eds) *Routledge Handbook of South-South Relations* (2018): 1966.

¹⁴⁹ Lei no 9.474, de 22 de julho de 1997, 'Define mecanismos para a implementação do Estatuto dos Refugiados de 1951, e determina outras providências', Art. 1 (III) (Brazil). See further Michael Reed-Hurtado, *The Cartagena declaration on refugees and the protection of people fleeing armed conflict and other situations of violence in Latin America* (UNHCR, Division of International Protections, 2013) 17.

Every person has the right, in case of pursuit not resulting from ordinary crimes, to seek and receive asylum in foreign territory, in accordance with the laws of each country and with international agreements.¹⁵⁰

Essentially mirroring Article XXVII of the ADHR, Article 22(7) of the ACHR provides for the right to seek and enjoy asylum in somewhat more limited terms than Article 14 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: Article 22(7) provides:

Every person has the right to seek and be granted asylum in a foreign territory, in accordance with the legislation of the state and international conventions, in the event he is being pursued for political offenses or related common crimes.¹⁵¹

Article 22(8) of the ADHR provides for the obligation of *non-refoulement* in broadly similar terms to those expressed in Article 33(1) of the Refugee Convention. Article 22(8) provides:

In no case may an alien be deported or returned to a country, regardless of whether or not it is his country of origin, if in that country his right to life or personal freedom is in danger of being violated because of his race, nationality, religion, social status, or political opinions.

Given the relatively narrow scope of the right to asylum expressed in Article 22(7), requiring that the applicant is being 'pursued for political offenses or related common crimes', early jurisprudence of the IACHR focused on the *state* right to grant asylum, rather than the *individual* right to seek and receive protection.¹⁵²

More recent practice, however, has significantly expanded the right to seek asylum in the Americas, with both the IACHR and IACtHR defining the right to asylum with reference to refugee protection instruments.¹⁵³ In the *Haitian*

¹⁵⁰ American Declaration on the Rights and Duties of Man, Bogotá, Colombia, adopted by Resolution XXX, Final Act of the Ninth International Conference of American States (Pan American Union), 30 March-2 May 1948, 1 Annals of the OAS 130 (1949).

¹⁵¹ American Convention on Human Rights, San José, Costa Rica, 22 November 1969, in force 18 July 1978, 36 Treaty Series 1.

¹⁵² Cantor and Barichello, 'Protection of Asylum Seekers under the Inter-American Human Rights System'. On the institution of asylum more broadly, see Roman Boed, 'The state of the right of asylum in international law' (1994) 5 Duke Journal of Comparative and International Law 1.

¹⁵³ Andreina De Leo and Juan Ruiz Ramos, 'Comparing the Inter-American Court opinion on diplomatic asylum applications with M.N. and Others v. Belgium before the ECtHR' EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy, available at <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/comparing-the-inter-american-court-opinion-on-diplomatic->

Interdictions case, which concerned the United States practice of maritime interdiction and return of Haitians, the IACHR held that the United States breached the applicants' right to asylum under the ADHR and ACHR, finding that the obligation of *non-refoulement* has 'no geographical limitations'.¹⁵⁴ Since then, both the Court and Commission have solidified a broader principle of the right to seek asylum in the Americas, in an effort to harmonise the Inter-American human rights system with regional and international standards, as well as UNHCR guidelines.¹⁵⁵

Perhaps most notably, in the leading 2013 case of *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia*, which concerned the summary removal of a Peruvian family seeking asylum by Bolivian authorities, the IACtHR drew on both Article 22(7) and 22(8) in finding that asylum seekers 'cannot be turned back at the border or expelled without an adequate and individualized analysis of their application.'¹⁵⁶ As discussed below, the Court further introduced a set of minimum procedural standards with respect to the asylum procedure.

In the IACtHR 2018 *Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 'The Institution Of Asylum And Its Recognition As a Human Right In The Inter-American System Of Protection'*, the Court further elucidated a number of principles on access to territorial and diplomatic asylum in OAS states. First, the Court held that the right to seek asylum applies extraterritorially and is thus enforceable where the individual is 'within the territory of the State or when in any way under its jurisdiction, without discrimination of any kind.'¹⁵⁷ Second, the IACtHR established that to ensure effectiveness, the asylum state owes a positive obligation to allow persons access to territory and asylum procedures, also in order to meet the obligations required of the *non-refoulement* principle.¹⁵⁸ Third, the Court imposed a limit on OAS states' migration control activities, stating that 'third States may not take action to prevent persons in need of international protection from seeking protection in other territories nor may they hide behind legal fictions to do so', with specific reference to maritime interception

[asylum-applications-with-m-n-and-others-v-belgium-before-the-ecthr/](#) accessed 22 September 2021.

¹⁵⁴ *Haitian Centre for Human Rights et al v USA* Case 10675 (Commission Report No 51/96, 13 March 1997) paras 157, 163.

¹⁵⁵ Jose H Fischel de Andrade, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Latin America', in Costello, Foster and McAdam, *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* 329.

¹⁵⁶ *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 153.

¹⁵⁷ *Advisory Opinion OC-25/18* of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador, Inter-American Court of Human Rights, available at <https://www.refworld.org/cases,IACRTHR,5c87ec454.html> accessed 23 September 2021 para 122.

¹⁵⁸ *Advisory Opinion OC-25/18* of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 122. See also *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 210.

in international waters.¹⁵⁹ Finally, the Court declared *non-refoulement* a *jus cogens* norm of international law.¹⁶⁰

The Cartagena Declaration does not squarely focus on access to asylum, but does emphasise the centrality of the principle of *non-refoulement*, with express inclusion of the prohibition of rejection at the frontier.¹⁶¹ The Declaration further states that the principle of *non-refoulement* 'should be acknowledged and observed as a rule of *jus cogens*.'¹⁶²

3.3 Asylum Procedures

With procedural standards for the asylum determination absent from the 1951 Convention,¹⁶³ the IACHR has sought to fill this normative gap through common regional standards drawn from the 1951 Convention, its 1967 Protocol and UNHCR guidance. Cantor and Barichello set out those procedural guarantees developed by the Commission in its jurisprudence and country reports, encompassing:

- the right of an asylum seeker to apply to the appropriate authorities for asylum,¹⁶⁴ later defined as a 'competent, independent and impartial decision-maker';¹⁶⁵
- the right of an asylum seeker to 'fair and transparent' procedure, with the opportunity to effectively make their claim, make representations and submit evidence;¹⁶⁶
- the right of access to legal aid for those asylum seekers who require it, notably unaccompanied children;¹⁶⁷

¹⁵⁹ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 122.

¹⁶⁰ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 98-9.

¹⁶¹ *Cartagena Declaration on Refugees* part II(5).

¹⁶² *Cartagena Declaration on Refugees* part II(5).

¹⁶³ See further Tan and Vedsted-Hansen, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards: Refugee and Human Rights Law Standards Applicable to Asylum Governance* 26-34; and Álvaro Botero and Jens Vedsted-Hansen, 'Asylum Procedures', (2021) in Costello, Foster and McAdam, *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* 588.

¹⁶⁴ *Michael Edwards et al v The Bahamas* Case 12067 (Commission Report No 48/01, 4 April 2001) para 171.

¹⁶⁵ Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, *Report on Terrorism and Human Rights* (OAS 2002) OEA/Ser.L/V/II.116/Doc.5 rev.1 corr., para 394.

¹⁶⁶ Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, *Report on Terrorism and Human Rights* (OAS 2002) OEA/Ser.L/V/II.116/Doc.5 rev.1 corr., para 394; Cantor and Barichello, 'Protection of Asylum Seekers under the Inter-American Human Rights System' 18-19.

¹⁶⁷ Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, *Report on Immigration in the United States: Detention and Due Process* (OAS 2010) OEA/Ser.L/II.Doc. 78/10, para 63.

- the right of an asylum seeker to receive adequate notification of the decision on their claim, based on 'sufficient substantiation' via an individualised and adequate assessment of the situation of risk;¹⁶⁸
- finally, as noted above, the right of an asylum seeker to the principle of *non-refoulement* until the determination of their asylum claim.¹⁶⁹

Following decades of standard-setting undertaken by the Commission, the IACtHR has recently weighed in on the asylum procedure in its caselaw.¹⁷⁰ In the *Pacheco Tineo Family* case, the IACtHR spelled out a number of 'due process minimum standards' required to respect the principle of *non-refoulement* and the right to asylum in the inter-American human rights system.

Drawing on the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol, national practice and UNHCR guidance, the Court found that OAS states are bound to provide of 'fair and efficient asylum proceedings' in line with due process standards found in other provisions of the ACHR.¹⁷¹ The Court stated:

any proceeding relating to the determination of the refugee status of a person entails an assessment and decision on the possible risk of affecting his most basic rights, such as life, and personal integrity and liberty. In this way, even if States may determine the proceedings and authorities to implement that right, in application of the principles of non-discrimination and due process they must ensure predictable proceedings, as well as coherence and objectivity in decision-making at each stage of the proceedings to avoid arbitrary decisions.¹⁷²

The Court further held that the asylum procedures must be undertaken by 'competent and previously established authorities' under prescribed 'proceedings that respect guarantees of due process of law.'¹⁷³ Beyond these

¹⁶⁸ Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, *Access to Justice and Social Inclusion: The Road towards Strengthening Democracy in Bolivia* (OAS 2007) OEA/Ser.L/V/II.Doc 34, para 410; Cantor and Barichello, 'Protection of Asylum Seekers under the Inter-American Human Rights System' 19-20

¹⁶⁹ *Haitian Centre for Human Rights et al v USA* Case 10675 (Commission Report No 51/96, 13 March 1997) para 163.

¹⁷⁰ Esraa Adnan Fangary, 'A Peculiar Leap in the Protection of Asylum Seekers: The Inter-American Court of Human Rights' Jurisprudence on the Protection of Asylum Seekers' (2021) *The Age of Human Rights Journal* 31.

¹⁷¹ Notably Article 8 ACHR provides for the right to a fair trial and Article 25 provides the right to judicial protection. *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 153.

¹⁷² *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 157.

¹⁷³ *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 158.

rather general standards, the Court went on to enumerate a number of obligations incumbents on states:

a) They must guarantee the applicant the necessary facilities, including the services of a competent interpreter, as well as, if appropriate, access to legal assistance and representation, in order to submit their request to the authorities. Thus, the applicant must receive the necessary guidance concerning the procedure to be followed, in words and in a way that he can understand and, if appropriate, he should be given the opportunity to contact a UNHCR representative;

b) The request must be examined, objectively, within the framework of the relevant procedure, by a competent and clearly identified authority, and requires a personal interview;

c) The decisions adopted by the competent organs must be duly and expressly founded;

d) In order to protect the rights of applicants who may be in danger, all stages of the asylum procedure must respect the protection of the applicant's personal information and the application, and the principle of confidentiality;

e) If the applicant is denied refugee status, he should be provided with information on how to file an appeal under the prevailing system and granted a reasonable period for this, so that the decision adopted can be formally adopted, and

f) The appeal for review must have suspensive effects and must allow the applicant to remain in the country until the competent authority has adopted the required decision, and even while the decision is being appealed, unless it can be shown that the request is manifestly unfounded.¹⁷⁴

The Court reiterated a number of these principles with respect to children asylum seekers in its 2018 Advisory Opinion,¹⁷⁵ with express reference to the best interests of the child and the right to be heard under Article 22 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC).¹⁷⁶

¹⁷⁴ *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 159 (references omitted).

¹⁷⁵ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 247.

¹⁷⁶ Convention on the Rights of the Child. Opened for signature 20 November 1989, 1577 UNTS 3 (entered into force 2 September 1990). The IACtHR held: 'States must adapt the proceedings on asylum or on the determination of refugee status, in order to provide children

With respect to Brazil's asylum procedures in particular, it is worth noting the innovative use of *prima facie* procedures recognising the refugee status of Venezuelans. Between June and December 2019, in light of serious and widespread violations of human rights in Venezuela, Brazilian authorities recognised the refugee status of 20,000 Venezuelans on the basis of *prima facie* procedures.¹⁷⁷

In sum, the IACHR has historically taken the lead in setting out non-binding standards for asylum procedures in the Americas, drawing on the implicit standards of the 1951 Conventions and its 1967 Protocol and UNHCR. Through the 2013 *Pacheco Tineo Family* case and its 2018 Advisory Opinion, however, the IACtHR has provided a comprehensive set of binding regional standards for asylum procedures, including with respect to children asylum seekers.¹⁷⁸

3.3.1 Safe third country concepts

While not implemented at regional level as in the case of Europe, discussed above, a number of bilateral safe third country agreements in the Americas function to deflect substantive asylum procedures to other states. Most notable is 2004 the US-Canada Safe Third Country Agreement (STCA), which prevents asylum seekers (subject to narrow exceptions for family and

with a real access to these procedures, allowing their specific situation to be considered. The Court finds that this obligation entails: not impeding entry to the country; if risk and needs are identified, the person should be given access to the State entity responsible for granting asylum or recognition of refugee status or other procedures that are suitable for the protection and specific attention to the circumstances of each case; priority processing of requests for asylum made by children as the main applicant; the availability of reception personnel in the entity, who can examine the child to determine her or his state of health; conducting an examination and interview endeavoring not to cause further trauma or revictimization; having available a place to accommodate the applicant, if they do not have one; issuing an identity document to avoid return; studying the case, with sufficient flexibility as regards the evidence; assigning an independent and trained guardian in the case of unaccompanied or separated children; if refugee status is granted, proceed to carry out family reunification procedures, if necessary in view of the best interest of the child; and lastly, seeking a durable solution, such as voluntary repatriation, resettlement or social integration, in accordance with the determination of the best interest of the child.' Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 261.

¹⁷⁷ On *prima facie* procedures, see UNHCR, *Handbook on Procedures and Criteria for Determining Refugee Status under the 1951 Convention and the 1967 Protocol relating to the Status of Refugees*, para 44; UNHCR, *Guidelines on International Protection No. 11: Prima Facie Recognition of Refugee Status* (HCR/GIP/15/11), June 2015. For a detailed account of Brazil's asylum governance, see Natália Medina Araújo, Brazil - Country Fiche (January 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_BRAZIL_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 16 August 2021

¹⁷⁸ See further Fangary, 'A Peculiar Leap in the Protection of Asylum Seekers: The Inter-American Court of Human Rights' Jurisprudence on the Protection of Asylum Seekers'

unaccompanied minors) from seeking protection at official border crossings on the Canada-US border.¹⁷⁹ The STCA operates on the basis that the US is a safe third country and has repeatedly been the subject of litigation in Canada, including with respect to the deterioration of conditions for refugee claimants in the United States during the Trump Administration.¹⁸⁰

In 2019, the United States entered into a bilateral Asylum Cooperative Arrangements (ACAs) with Guatemala, Honduras and El Salvador allowing for the transfer of asylum seekers from the United States without the possibility of applying for asylum.¹⁸¹ The ACAs were also based on the safe third country concept and between November 2019 and March 2020 939 asylum seekers were transferred under the US-Guatemala agreement.¹⁸² The operation of the ACA was suspended in March 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic and all ACAs were subsequently rescinded the by incoming Biden Administration.

Also in 2019, Peru began informal implementation of the safe third country concept for Venezuelans seeking protection via the country's land border with Ecuador.¹⁸³ Peruvian authorities initiated a pre-screening procedure at the border for Venezuelans, refusing to hear the asylum claims of those protection seekers who had transited through Colombia and Ecuador, on the basis of the safe third country concept.¹⁸⁴

3.4 The Scope of International Protection

While the Inter-American Human Rights System does include a substantive right to 'seek and receive asylum',¹⁸⁵ the IACtHR and IACHR have not comprehensively set out the scope of that protection. Nevertheless, jurisprudence does provide some important standards on the question of who benefits from international protection in the Americas.

First, as a general matter, both the Court and Commission have interpreted the scope of international protection in line with the inclusion criteria set out in the

¹⁷⁹ For an overview of the operation of the STCA, see Audrey Macklin and Joshua Blum, Canada - Country Fiche (January 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_CANADA_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 16 August 2021.

¹⁸⁰ Ibid.

¹⁸¹ See, for example, Agreement Between the Government of the United States of America and the Republic of Guatemala on Cooperation Regarding the Examination of Protection Claims, 26 July 2019.

¹⁸² Refugees International and Human Rights Watch, Failure of Protection under the US-Guatemala Asylum Cooperative Agreement, (2020).

¹⁸³ Luisa Feline Freier, Eleni Karageorgiou, and Kate Ogg, "Challenging the legality of externalisation in Oceania, Europe and South America: an impossible task?." *Forced Migration Review* 68 (2021): 23-26.

¹⁸⁴ Ibid,

¹⁸⁵ See 3.2 above.

1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol as well as, in the case of Latin American states, the expanded definition recommended by the Cartagena Declaration, discussed below. For example, in its 2018 Advisory Opinion the IACtHR held that a state is obliged to grant international protection:

when the person qualifies for it, either under the criteria of the traditional or the extended Cartagena definition... The Court has also concluded that, once a person's refugee status is determined, he or she shall remain such unless he or she falls within the scope of one of the cessation clauses.¹⁸⁶

Second, the IACtHR has recently stated that refugee status should be granted to family members on the basis of the principle of family unity. In the *Pacheco Tineo Family* case, the Court suggested that derivative status 'may' flow to family members, particularly children.¹⁸⁷ However, in its 2018 Advisory Opinion, the Court used the language of obligation in this regard stating:

It is the obligation of the host State to grant international protection when the person qualifies for it, either under the criteria of the traditional or the extended Cartagena definition... and benefit other family members with that recognition, in accordance with the principle of family unity.¹⁸⁸

Third, somewhat exceptionally, refugee status in the Americas has extraterritorial effect. In its 2018 Advisory Opinion, the Court noted the positive obligation of OAS states 'to maintain and give continuity to the refugee status determination, which also is in effect extraterritorially, unless any of the cessation clauses are incurred'.¹⁸⁹

At the sub-regional level, inspired by the definition of refugeehood put forward by the OAU Convention, the Cartagena Declaration builds on the Refugee Convention definition to include:

persons who have fled their country because their lives, safety or freedom have been threatened by generalized violence, foreign aggression, internal

¹⁸⁶ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 123.

¹⁸⁷ *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 159.

¹⁸⁸ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 123.

¹⁸⁹ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 123.

conflicts, massive violation of human rights or other circumstances which have seriously disturbed public order.¹⁹⁰

A number of elements expand the scope of protection under the Cartagena Declaration over the Refugee Convention definition. Most notably, the five 'situational events' that give rise to refugeehood are more reflective of the realities of contemporary displacement than individualised persecution on a Convention ground. The scenarios contained in Conclusion III (3) are characterised by 'indiscriminate, unpredictable or collective nature of the risks they present' both to individuals and groups.¹⁹¹ Asylum seekers need only demonstrate one of the five situational events to meet this criterion and, as with the OAU Convention, this definition is based on objective and often generalised conditions in the country of origin rather than an individualised fear of persecution.¹⁹²

Moreover, the risk standard within the Cartagena Declaration is considered lower than that of the Refugee Convention. Rather than the 'well-founded fear', the term 'threat' requires a lower threshold of proof. In general, proximity to the situational event is sufficient to justify international protection under the Cartagena definition.¹⁹³

Brazil has partially incorporated this broader Cartagena Declaration definition into its the Refugee Act of 1997, with Article 1(III) providing that, in addition to the 1951 Convention definition, a refugee is recognised where 'due to a serious and widespread violation of human rights, he is obliged to leave his country of nationality to seek refuge in another country.'¹⁹⁴

Finally, in some American states complementary protection status is also provided for in national law. In Canada¹⁹⁵ and the United States,¹⁹⁶ a narrow group of people in refugee-like situations receive international protection on the basis of the principle of *non-refoulement* in the Convention Against

¹⁹⁰ *Cartagena Declaration on Refugees, Colloquium on the International Protection of Refugees in Central America, Mexico and Panama*, 22 November 1984, Conclusion III (3).

¹⁹¹ UNHCR, *Summary Conclusions on the interpretation of the extended refugee definition in the 1984 Cartagena Declaration* para 8.

¹⁹² Eduardo Arboleda, 'The Cartagena Declaration of 1984 and its Similarities to the 1969 OAU Convention-A Comparative Perspective' *International Journal of Refugee Law* 7 (1995) 87.

¹⁹³ UNHCR, *Summary Conclusions on the interpretation of the extended refugee definition in the 1984 Cartagena Declaration* para 28.

¹⁹⁴ Lei nº 9474/97 article 1(III).

¹⁹⁵ *Immigration and Refugee Protection Act*, SC 2001, c 27, s 97.

¹⁹⁶ *Immigration and Nationality Act*, 8 CFR §§ 208.16, 208.17.

Torture.¹⁹⁷ In Mexico,¹⁹⁸ complementary protection is conceived of more broadly, in line with the human rights law prohibition against transfer to a real risk of torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. However, these complementary protection statuses may be legally or practically limited. For example, complementary protection in the United States only extends to protection against return to a risk of torture in line with Article 1 of the Convention Against Torture,¹⁹⁹ rather than the broader standard of inhuman degrading treatment or punishment contained in, for example Article 7 of the ICCPR.²⁰⁰

In sum, the inter-American human rights system defines the scope of international protection in line with the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol, while at the sub-regional level Latin American states employ, to varying degrees,²⁰¹ the expanded Cartagena definition. Finally, a number of states outside the Cartagena framework provide for complementary protection status.

3.5 The Content of International Protection

At the inter-American level, both the IACHR and IACtHR have aligned international protection standards with those contained in the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol. Accordingly, the accumulative protection standards applying to refugees under the Refugee Convention according to the factual and legal nature of the refugee's attachment to the country of asylum are of general application to refugees in the Americas.²⁰²

¹⁹⁷ See further Jane McAdam, *Complementary Protection in International Refugee Law* (Oxford University Press 2007); Jane McAdam, 'Complementary Protection' in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam, *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (Oxford University Press 2021) 661-678; Advisory Opinion OC-21/14, "Rights and Guarantees of Children in the Context of Migration and/or in Need of International Protection", OC-21/1419, Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR), August 2014 para 240.

¹⁹⁸ Ley sobre Refugiados Protección Complementaria y Asilo Político (Mexico), articles 28–32.

¹⁹⁹ The Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment. Opened for signature 10 December 1984, 1486 UNTS 85 (entered into force 26 June 1987); Bill Frelick, 'What's Wrong with Temporary Protected Status and How to Fix It: Exploring a Complementary Protection Regime' (2020) 8 *Journal on Migration and Human Security* 42, 46.

²⁰⁰ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (adopted 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976) 999 UNTS 171 (ICCPR).

²⁰¹ Jose H Fischel de Andrade, Regional Refugee Regimes: Latin America in Costello, Foster and McAdam, *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* 332-3.

²⁰² Tan and Vedsted-Hansen, *Catalogue of International and Regional Legal Standards: Refugee and Human Rights Law Standards Applicable to Asylum Governance* 50-9. See further see James C. Hathaway, *The Rights of Refugees under International Law* (2nd ed., CUP 2021) 173-

3.6 Resettlement and complementary pathways

The inter-American human rights system does not include a regional mechanism for resettlement or complementary pathways in the Americas. However, in the context of the Cartagena framework, the 2004 Mexico Declaration and Plan of Action introduced a regional resettlement mechanism. Brazil led the initiative, proposing a Solidarity Resettlement Programme with a focus on resettlement of refugees from the region, notably Colombia, Guatemala, Honduras, and El Salvador.²⁰³ The Programme, in operation between 2005 and 2014, resettled 1,151 refugees, with the vast majority coming from Colombia, to Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Paraguay and Uruguay.²⁰⁴ At the national level, both Brazil (resettlement and humanitarian visas) and Canada (resettlement, community sponsorship and education pathways) have resettlement or complementary pathways to admission for refugees.²⁰⁵

3.7 Conclusions

The right of asylum in the Americas is characterised by two overlapping regional protection systems: the inter-American Human Rights System, comprising the IACHR and IACtHR binding OAS member states and, in Latin America, the Cartagena Declaration framework.

With respect to access to asylum, in contrast to the European Convention on Human Rights, both the ADHR and ACHR prescribe a specific right to seek and receive asylum.²⁰⁶ Moreover, the IACtHR has interpreted the ancillary principle of *non-refoulement* as a *jus cogens* norm of international law.²⁰⁷ Both the Commission and Court have further interpreted the right to seek asylum as

219; Guy S. Goodwin-Gill and Jane McAdam, *The Refugee in International Law* (4th ed., OUP 2021) 595-9.

²⁰³ Thais Silva Menezes and Stylianos Kostas. "The future of the Brazilian resettlement programme." *Forced Migration Review* 56 (2017): 51-52.

²⁰⁴ María José Marcogliese, "The Solidarity Resettlement Programme, and alternatives, in Latin America." *Forced Migration Review* 54 (2017): 54.

²⁰⁵ See further Natália Medina Araújo, Brazil - Country Fiche (January 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_BRAZIL_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 16 August 2021; and Audrey Macklin and Joshua Blum, Canada - Country Fiche (January 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_CANADA_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 16 August 2021.

On Brazil's resettlement programme, see Jubilit, Liliana L.; Zamur, Andrea C. G. Brazil's Refugee Resettlement: Power, Humanitarianism and Regional Leadership. In: Garnier, Adèle; Jubilit, Liliana L.; Sandvik, Kristin B. (Eds.). *Refugee Resettlement: Power, Politics and Humanitarian Governance*, 2018: 70-91.

²⁰⁶ ADHR article XXVII and ACHR article 22(7).

²⁰⁷ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 98-9.

applying extraterritorially, including on the high seas,²⁰⁸ as well as finding that the combined right to seek asylum and *non-refoulement* principle entails positive obligations to allow persons access to territory and asylum procedures.²⁰⁹

In relation to asylum procedures, while the IACHR has historically taken the lead in setting out non-binding standards, the IACtHR has recently produced rules on regional procedural standards in the 2013 *Pacheco Tineo Family* case and its 2018 Advisory Opinion. Through this jurisprudence, the Court has provided a detailed set of binding regional standards for asylum procedures, including with respect to children asylum seekers.²¹⁰

With respect to the scope of international protection, the inter-American human rights system defines the scope of international protection in line with the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol. At the sub-regional level, some Latin American states employ the expanded Cartagena definition. Additionally, a number of states provide for complementary protection status.

Finally, in relation to the content of international protection, the inter-American Human Rights System and the Cartagena Declaration reflect the protective standards set out as gradually accruing to the Refugee in the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol.

4 THE RIGHT OF ASYLUM IN AFRICA

4.1 Introduction

The African regional protection system for refugees is based on the 1969 *OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa* (OAU Convention) in addition to the 1951 Refugee Convention.²¹¹ The OAU Convention was the world's first regional refugee protection instrument and,

²⁰⁸ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 122; *Haitian Centre for Human Rights et al v USA* Case 10675 (Commission Report No 51/96, 13 March 1997) paras 157, 163.

²⁰⁹ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 122. See also *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 210.

²¹⁰ See further Fangary, 'A Peculiar Leap in the Protection of Asylum Seekers: The Inter-American Court of Human Rights' Jurisprudence on the Protection of Asylum Seekers'

²¹¹ 1969 OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa (adopted 10 September 1969, entered into force 20 June 1974) 1001 UNTS 45 (OAU Convention).

to this day, it is one of only two legally binding regional regimes.²¹² It was intended to form an effective complement to the Refugee Convention addressing issues specific to Africa.²¹³ Fifty-one of the 55 African Union (AU) Member States have ratified the Refugee Convention, whereas 48 States have ratified the OAU Convention.²¹⁴

In addition, the *African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights*,²¹⁵ the *Women's Protocol*²¹⁶ and the *Children's Charter*²¹⁷ provide guarantees for refugees, while the *Kampala Convention* is concerned with the protection needs of internally displaced persons.²¹⁸

The OAU Convention does not provide for a supervisory body like UNHCR under Article 35 of the Refugee Convention. However, according to Article VII of the OAU Convention, Member States must report statistical data to the OAU Secretariat (now Secretary General of the AU) on the conditions of refugees, the implementation of the Convention and the applicable refugee law. Furthermore, Article IX of the OAU Convention provides for the settlement of disputes between the Member States in front of the OAU Commission, similar to Article 38 of the Refugee Convention before the ICJ.

The supervisory treaty body under the African Charter is the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR). According to Article 56 of the African Charter, it has jurisdiction over individual complaints and, according to Article 47 ff, over inter-state conflicts. It is competent to review communicated cases, also on the basis of other international human rights laws than the African Charter.²¹⁹ However, the ACHPR's recommendations are

²¹² Marina Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (First Edition, Oxford University Press 2021) 279. The European regional protection is the other binding regime; see Chapter 2 of this working paper. See Jean Francois Durieux and Agnès Hurwitz, 'How Many Is Too Many? African and European Legal Responses to Mass Influxes of Refugees' (2004) 47 *German yearbook of international law* 105.

²¹³ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 283. See OAU Convention, art VIII(2).

²¹⁴ *ibid* 281 FN 7.

²¹⁵ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (adopted 27 June 1981, entered into force 21 October 1986) 21 ILM 58 (African Charter); see *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa (on behalf of Sierra Leonean refugees in Guinea) v. Guinea*, Comm no 249/02 (ACHPR, December 2004) para 68 regarding the application of the Charter to refugees.

²¹⁶ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People's Rights on the Rights of Women in Africa (adopted 11 July 2003, entered into force 25 November 2005) OAU Doc CAB/LEG/66.6 (Women's Protocol).

²¹⁷ African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child (adopted 11 July 1990, entered into force 29 November 1999) OAU doc CAB/LEG/24.9/49 (Children's Charter).

²¹⁸ African Union Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa (adopted 23 October 2009, entered into force 6 December 2012) (Kampala Convention)

²¹⁹ African Charter, art 60.

generally viewed as non-binding, despite the obligation of state parties to 'give effect' to the treaty pursuant to Article 1 of the African Charter.²²⁰

The creation of the African Court on Human and People's Rights (ACtHPR) was an attempt to solve this issue.²²¹ Whereas its decisions are binding, direct access to the court is limited. The African Commission, state parties to the 1998 Protocol and intergovernmental organisations may refer cases to it, while individuals or NGOs can only refer cases regarding countries that have accepted the Court's jurisdiction pursuant to Article 5 (3) of the 1998 Protocol.²²²

In contrast to the Refugee Convention, the OAU Convention addresses the necessity for solidarity and responsibility-sharing in the body of the treaty itself. Article II(4) states:

Where a Member State *finds difficulty in continuing to grant asylum* to refugees, such Member State may appeal directly to other Member States and through the OAU, and such other Member States shall in the spirit of African solidarity and international co-operation *take appropriate measures to lighten the burden* of the Member State granting asylum.²²³

Article II(4) grants Member States the possibility to ask for assistance if overwhelmed and at the same time obliges other Member States to take measures in that regard. The issue of solidarity and responsibility-sharing has only been addressed recently on the international level with the GCR, a non-binding instrument.²²⁴

²²⁰ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 289 with reference to *Civil Liberties Organization v Nigeria*, Comm no 129/94 (ACHPR, 22 March 1995) paras 16 ff; Frans Viljoen and Lurette Louw, 'State Compliance with the Recommendations of the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, 1994-2004' (2007) 101 *American Journal of International Law* 1, 2.

²²¹ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and People's rights on the Establishment of an African Court on Human and People's Rights (adopted 10 June 1998, entered into force 25 January 2004) OAU doc OAU/LEG/EXP/AFCHPR/PROT (1998 Protocol).

²²² 1998 Protocol, arts 5 (1) and (3), 34 (6). In 2021, these were only eight countries: Burkina Faso, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Malawi and Tunisia; Rwanda, Tanzania, Côte d'Ivoire and Benin had withdrawn their declarations in the recent years. See further *Request for Advisory Opinion by the Centre for Human Rights of the University of Pretoria and the Coalition of African Lesbians*, App no 002/15 (ACtHPR, 28 September 2017) paras 52 ff; *Femi Falana v African Union*, App no 001/11 (ACtHPR, 26 June 2012) para 75; *Michelot Yogogombaye v Senegal*, App no 001/08 (ACtHPR, 15 December 2009) paras 37 ff.

²²³ Emphasis added.

²²⁴ See Fatima Khan and Cecile Sackeyfio, 'Situating the Global Compact on Refugees in Africa: Will It Make a Difference to the Lives of Refugees "Languishing in Camps"?' (2021) 65 *Journal of African Law* 35. *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa (on behalf of Sierra Leonean refugees in Guinea) v. Guinea*, Comm no 249/02 (ACHPR, December 2004); *Curtis Francis Doebbler v Sudan*, Comm no 235/00 (ACHPR, 25 November 2009).

Furthermore, Article II(5) of the OAU Convention provides a preliminary solution as the refugee may be granted temporary residence in the country of first arrival. This temporary reception mechanism has only been used in one instance. The Emergency Transit Mechanism (ETM) programme for asylum seekers in Libya to Niger and Rwanda resembles this temporary reception mechanism. Under memoranda of understanding with Niger and Rwanda, respectively, and the AU and UNHCR, vulnerable asylum seekers are evacuated from detention in Libya to Niger and Rwanda for asylum procedures and local integration or resettlement.²²⁵

Another addition is Article V of the OAU Convention on voluntary repatriation with Paragraph 1 stating: 'The essentially voluntary character of repatriation shall be respected in all cases and no refugee shall be repatriated against his will.' The rest of the Article holds several rules on how voluntary repatriation should take place. A recent study in South Africa, however, showed that cases of truly voluntary repatriation are few.²²⁶

South Africa, one of the focus countries of the ASILE project, is a Member of the African Union (AU). It is party to the African Charter and the Protocol on the establishment of an African Court. However, it has not accepted jurisdiction for cases submitted by NGOs with observer status or individuals pursuant to Article 5(3) of the Optional Protocol. It has ratified both the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1969 OAU Convention and implemented them in national legislation.²²⁷

4.2 Access to Asylum

The OAU Convention's wording exceeds the protection standard of the Refugee Convention regarding access to asylum. Article I(6) of the OAU Convention obliges the Contracting State to determine refugee status, whereas Article II(1) demands their 'best endeavours (...) to receive refugees and to secure the

²²⁵ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 286 f; see African Union, 'Government of Rwanda, UNHCR, and African Union Agree to Evacuate Refugees and Asylum Seekers in Libya' (10 September 2019) <<https://au.int/en/pressreleases/20190910/government-rwanda-unhcr-and-african-union-agree-evacuate-refugees-and-0>> accessed 4 November 2021.

UNHCR, Emergency Transit Mechanism, Factsheet (December 2020) https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/UNHCR%20Niger_Factsheet%20Update_ETM_December%202020.pdf accessed 11 April 2022.

²²⁶ See further Fatima Khan, 'Is Voluntary Repatriation the Preferred Durable Solution? The View of Refugees in South Africa' (2020) 6 African Human Mobility Review 2, available at <https://sihma.org.za/journals/04%20Is%20Voluntary%20Repatriation%20the%20Preferred%20Durable%20Solution%2002.pdf> accessed 7 April 2022.

²²⁷ Fatima Khan and Nandi Rayner, South Africa – Country Fiche (October 2020) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Country-Fiche_South-Africa_Final_Pub.pdf accessed 20 October 2021, 2.

settlement' of refugees.²²⁸ In addition, the African Charter in Article 12(3) holds a right to 'seek and obtain asylum'.²²⁹ Hence, the African regional protection system seems to provide an individual right to asylum. However, this is contested because the right is subjected to the domestic laws of the country where asylum is sought.²³⁰

Furthermore, the OAU Convention prohibits *refoulement* in Article II(3) stating:

No person shall be subjected by a Member State to measures such as *rejection at the frontier, return or expulsion*, which would compel him to return to or remain in a territory *where his life, physical integrity or liberty* would be threatened for the reasons set out in Article I, paragraphs 1 and 2.²³¹

This wording goes beyond the protections offered by Article 33 of the Refugee Convention, since it not only protects 'life and freedom', but also 'physical integrity'.²³² The prohibition further explicitly includes 'rejection at the frontier' – a problem about which the drafters of the Refugee Convention remained oblique.²³³

The principle of *non-refoulement* has further been developed according to the regional human rights regime, including in deportation cases. Article 5 of the African Charter states:

Every individual shall have the right to the *respect of the dignity inherent* in a human being and to the recognition of his legal status. All forms of exploitation and degradation of man particularly slavery, slave trade, *torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading punishment and treatment* shall be prohibited.²³⁴

²²⁸ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 286. See Section 4.5 below on Article II (6) of the OAU Convention.

²²⁹ See on the application in South Africa Chun Luk, South Africa – Country Note (April 2021) available at https://www.asileproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Country-Note_South_Africa.pdf accessed 20 October 2021.

²³⁰ Marina Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (Oxford University Press 2018) 133 f; compare however Ademola Abass and Dominique Mystris, 'The African Union Legal Framework for Protecting Asylum Seekers' in Ademola Abass and Francesca Ippolito (eds), *Regional Approaches to the Protection of Asylum Seekers: An International Legal Perspective* (Ashgate 2016) 23.

²³¹ Emphasis added.

²³² Compare Refugee Convention, art 33 (1).

²³³ See Hathaway, *Rights of Refugees* 428 ff.

²³⁴ Emphasis added; see application of Article 5 African Charter to deportation cases in *John K Modise v Botswana*, Comm no 97/93 (ACHPR, 6 November 2000) para 92 and *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa v Angola*, Comm no 292/2004 (ACHPR, 22 May 2008) paras 49 ff, 84; for South Africa see *Abdi and Another v Minister of Home Affairs and Others*, Case no 734/2010 (Supreme Court of Appeal of South Africa, 15 February 2011) ZASCA 2; *Minister of Home Affairs and Others v Watchenuka and Others*, Case no 010/2003 (Supreme Court of Appeal of South Africa, 28 November 2003) ZASCA 142.

In addition, Article 12(3) and (4) of the African Charter hold a prohibition of expulsion for non-nationals lawfully on the territory without due process and a prohibition of mass expulsion.²³⁵

Article 18 of the African Charter further protects family life and in conjunction with Article 18 f of the Children's Charter prohibits *refoulement*, where it would lead to the separation of children from their families.²³⁶

4.3 Asylum Procedures

The OAU Convention does not provide specific procedural rules with respect to asylum procedures. However, the ACHPR has developed procedural guarantees based on the right to a fair trial under Article 7(1) of the African Charter, which holds:²³⁷

1. Every individual shall have the right to have his cause heard. This comprises: (a) the *right to an appeal to competent national organs* against acts of violating his fundamental rights as recognized and guaranteed by conventions, laws, regulations and customs in force; (b) the right to be *presumed innocent until proved guilty* by a competent court or tribunal; (c) the right to defense, including the right to be defended by counsel of his choice; (d) the right to be tried within a reasonable time by an impartial court or tribunal. (...) ²³⁸

These procedural safeguards are essential to access the enjoyment of substantive rights, such as *non-refoulement* pursuant to Article 5 of the African Charter. In *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa v Angola*, the African Commission held that, although there was no absolute right to enter the territory according to Article 5 of the African Charter, due process must be regarded during the denial of entry or expulsion:

Even in such extreme circumstances as expulsion, however, the affected individuals should be allowed to challenge the order/decision to expel them

²³⁵ *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa v Angola*, Comm no 292/2004 (ACHPR, 22 May 2008) paras 63 ff; *Organisation Mondiale Contre la Torture and Others v Rwanda*, Comm no 27/89, 49/91 and 99/93 (ACHPR, 31 October 1996) para 30; see further *Rencontre Africaine pour la Défense des Droits de l'Homme (RADDHO) v. Zambia*, Comm no 71/92 (ACHPR, 31 October 1996) para 23.

²³⁶ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 288. See *Union inter- Africaine des droits de l'homme and Others v Angola*, Comm no 159/96 (ACHPR, 11 November 1997) para 17; *Sudan Human Rights Organisation & Centre on Housing Rights and Evictions (COHRE) v Sudan*, Comm no 279/ 03, 296/ 05, (ACHPR, 27 May 2009) paras 213 ff.

²³⁷ Botero and Vedsted-Hansen (n 41) 599. See eg *Good v Republic of Botswana*, Comm no 313/05 (ACHPR, 26 May 2010) paras 160 ff; *Organisation Mondiale Contre la Torture and Others v Rwanda*, Comm no 27/89, 49/91 and 99/93 (ACHPR, 31 October 1996) para 34.

²³⁸ Emphasis added. The right to be defended also applies to administrative cases according to *ibid* 601 with reference to *Media Rights Agenda v Nigeria*, Comm no 224/98 (ACHPR, 6 November 2000) para 56.

before competent authorities, or have their cases reviewed, and have access to legal counsel, among others. Such procedural safeguards aim at making sure that nonnationals enjoy the equal protection of the law in their country of residence, ensure that their daily lives are not arbitrarily interfered with, and that they are not sent back/deported/expelled to countries or places they are likely to suffer from torture, inhuman or degrading treatment, or death, among others.²³⁹

A UNHCR study from 2013 conducted in 45 African states showed that these countries generally adjudicate refugee claims on an individual basis. At that time, 35 had state-run systems in place, whereas in 10 countries UNHCR was conducting the refugee status determination.²⁴⁰

The High Court of South Africa has pointed out procedural safeguards as well. In *Radjabu*, it particularly elaborated on the requirement of an interpreter to ensure a fair trial and, in *Harerimana*, the Court stated the necessity of the individual to fully understand the procedures, their rights and responsibilities as well as the presented evidence.²⁴¹ Yet, continuous procedural obstacles receiving protection are reported from South Africa, such as refusal of delayed applications, unlawful pre-screening forms, accelerated border procedures, limitations to applications per day and the closure of Refugee Reception Offices.²⁴²

4.4 The Scope of International Protection

²³⁹ *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa v Angola*, Comm no 292/2004 (ACHPR, 22 May 2008) para 84; see further *Union inter- Africaine des droits de l'homme and Others v Angola*, Comm no 159/96 (ACHPR, 11 November 1997) para 19; see further *Rencontre Africaine pour la Défense des Droits de l'Homme (RADDHO) v. Zambia*, Comm no 71/92 (ACHPR, 31 October 1996) paras 29 ff; compare Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 132.

²⁴⁰ Marina Sharpe, 'The 1969 OAU Refugee Convention and the Protection of People Fleeing Armed Conflict and Other Situations of Violence in the Context of Individual Refugee Status Determination' (2013) 30 7.

²⁴¹ *Radjabu v The Chairperson of the Standing Committee for Refugee Affairs*, Case no 8830/2010 (High Court of South Africa, 4 September 2014) ZAWCHC 134; *Harerimana v Chairperson of the Refugee Appeal Board and Others*, Case no 10972/2013 (High Court of South Africa, 11 December 2013) ZAWCHC 209, para 13 ff. Compare, however, Roni Amit, 'No Refuge: Flawed Status Determination and the Failures of South Africa's Refugee System to Provide Protection' (2011) 23 *International Journal of Refugee Law* 458, who finds the South African procedures flawed.

²⁴² *Khan and Rayner* (n 231) 11 f, 20; see *Ersumo v Minister of Home Affairs*, Case no 69/2012 (Supreme Court of Appeal of South Africa, 28 March 2012) ZASCA 31; *Tatira v Ngozwana*, Case no 12960/16 (High Court of South Africa, 12 December 2006) ZAGPHC 136; *Kiliko and Others v Minister of Home Affairs and Others*, Case no 2739/05 (Western Cape High Court of South Africa, 4 March 2008) ZAWCHC 124; *Scalabrini Centre, Cape Town and Others v Minister of Home Affairs and Others*, Case no 1107/2016 (Supreme Court of Appeal of South Africa, 29 September 2017) ZASCA 126; *Ruta v Minister of Home Affairs*, Case no CCT02/18 (South African Constitutional Court, 20 December 2018) ZACC 52.

The OAU Convention in Article I(1) provides a definition of refugeehood following the definition in Article 1A(2) of the Refugee Convention. Article I(2) of the OAU Convention, however, goes on to extend the definition in the following terms:

The term “refugee” shall also apply to *every person* who, owing to external aggression, occupation, foreign domination or *events seriously disturbing public order in either part or the whole* of his country of origin or nationality, is compelled to leave his place of habitual residence in order to seek refuge in another place outside his country of origin or nationality.²⁴³

Hence, the scope of the OAU text is broader than the scope for protection under the Refugee Convention.²⁴⁴ ‘Every person’ includes people fleeing from within the continent or from outside and thus ensures a broad application *ratione personae*.²⁴⁵

Also *ratione materiae*, the OAU has a broad scope of application. In particular, the phrase ‘events seriously disturbing public order’ expands the scope beyond individual persecution to generalised violence.²⁴⁶ Other circumstances like natural disasters may fall within the scope of this provision,²⁴⁷ however this remains a contested question.²⁴⁸

Additionally, the phrase ‘in either part or the whole’ can be read to exclude the application of internal flight alternative (IFA) concepts.²⁴⁹ Article I(3) of the OAU Convention further takes into account persons with multiple nationalities who cannot find protection in any of the respective countries.

²⁴³ Emphasis added.

²⁴⁴ Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 35 ff; Tamara Wood, ‘Expanding Protection in Africa: Case Studies of the Implementation of the 1969 African Refugee Convention’s Expanded Refugee Definition’ (2014) 26 *International Journal of Refugee Law* 555, 559 ff.

²⁴⁵ Sharpe, ‘Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa’ (n 216) 284.

²⁴⁶ *ibid* mentions Ghana, Guinea, Liberia and Togo using this ‘prima facie’ approach for refugees from Côte d’Ivoire.

²⁴⁷ See Tamara Wood, ‘Protection and Disasters in the Horn of Africa: Norms and Practice for Addressing Cross-Border Displacement in Disaster Contexts’ (The Nansen Initiative) Technical Paper <http://www.nanseninitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/190215_Technical_Paper_Tamara_Wood.pdf> accessed 3 November 2021; see further Sanjula Weerasinghe, ‘Refugee Law in a Time of Climate Change, Disaster and Conflict’ (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees 2020) 40 11 ff <<https://www.unhcr.org/protection/globalconsult/5fdc70eb4/40-refugee-law-time-climate-change-disaster-conflict.html>> accessed 5 November 2021.

²⁴⁸ Alice Edwards, ‘Refugee Status Determination in Africa’ (2006) 14 *African Journal of International and Comparative Law* 204, 225 ff; Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 49 ff.

²⁴⁹ Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 36.

Hence, the OAU Convention's refugee definition broadens the scope of application in theory. For this reason, it has been largely viewed as more humanitarian and less political than the Refugee Convention's definition and has functioned as a model for refugee regimes elsewhere.²⁵⁰ Yet, it is unclear whether its theoretical scope is reflected in the implementation practice amongst the state parties.²⁵¹ Furthermore, there is presently little jurisprudence interpreting the OAU Convention or regional refugee rights overall and also the scholarship on the OAU Convention's refugee definition has been criticised for falling behind the changing circumstances on the continent.²⁵²

It is further notable that the OAU Convention in Article III(1) holds a prohibition of 'subversive activities'. At the time of drafting, Member States were concerned that refugees would use host countries as a base to organise political or military action against the regimes in their country of origin.²⁵³ Nowadays, this prohibition must be interpreted in connection with fundamental rights, such as freedom of expression, association and assembly.²⁵⁴

South Africa has incorporated the OAU Convention's refugee definition, including the extended protection by Article I(2).²⁵⁵ In *Harerimana*, the South African High Court interpreted the extended refugee definition to be governed by objective factors.²⁵⁶ In a more recent case, the South African Supreme Court of Appeal interprets in further detail how the state must consider the extended definition.²⁵⁷ Nevertheless, a lack of implementation and multiple flaws in the process of refugee status determination are reported.²⁵⁸ Regarding subversive activities, Section 4(2) of the 2019 South African Refugees Act 1998 (Refugee Regulations) includes a ban on political activity for refugees and asylum seekers.²⁵⁹

²⁵⁰ Tamara Wood, 'Who Is a Refugee in Africa? A Principled Framework for Interpreting and Applying Africa's Expanded Refugee Definition' (2019) 31 *International Journal of Refugee Law* 290, 293 f.

²⁵¹ *ibid* 295 f.

²⁵² *ibid* 297 ff; Abass and Mystris (n 234) 22 f. Compare *Radjabu v The Chairperson of the Standing Committee for Refugee Affairs*, Case no 8830/2010 (High Court of South Africa, 4 September 2014) ZAWCHC 134; *Harerimana v Chairperson of the Refugee Appeal Board and Others*, Case no 10972/2013 (High Court of South Africa, 11 December 2013) ZAWCHC 209.

²⁵³ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 282; Durieux and Hurwitz (n 216) 115.

²⁵⁴ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 284.

²⁵⁵ Tal Hanna Schreier, 'An Evaluation of South Africa's Application of the OAU Refugee Definition' (2008) 25 *Canada's Journal on Refugees* 53, 53.

²⁵⁶ *Harerimana v Chairperson of the Refugee Appeal Board and Others*, Case no 10972/2013 (High Court of South Africa, 11 December 2013) ZAWCHC 209 paras 11 f.

²⁵⁷ *Somali Association of South Africa and Others v The Refugee Appeal Board and Others*, Case no 585/2020 (SA Supreme Court of Appeal, 23 September 2021) ZASCA 124.

²⁵⁸ See Khan and Rayner (n 231) 22; Amit (n 245).

²⁵⁹ The Refugees Act 1998 (Refugee Regulations) 2019.

4.5 The Content of International Protection

Whereas the time of the OAU Convention's adoption is described as the 'golden age' of asylum in Africa, nowadays African states show more restrictive approaches when it comes to granting benefits to refugees.²⁶⁰ On the one hand, this tendency concerns individual status determination, as procedures become more regulated. On the other hand, it also affects the content of protection under the Convention with the approach to granting rights becoming more restrictive.²⁶¹

The OAU Convention does not hold a detailed catalogue of rights for refugees comparable to the Refugee Convention. It grants protection from *refoulement* including the possibility of temporary reception,²⁶² protection from discrimination,²⁶³ a right to travel documents²⁶⁴ and a right to voluntary repatriation²⁶⁵.²⁶⁶ It further has been suggested that the wording of Article II(1) of the OAU Convention implies a right to seek asylum²⁶⁷ and to assistance in resettlement.²⁶⁸

Article II (6) of the OAU Convention states:

For reasons of security, countries of asylum shall, as far as possible, settle refugees at a reasonable distance from the frontier of their country of origin.

Although this provision suggests that refugees should live at a distance from the border that provides for their safety and prevents conflict following them across the border, it also implies that forced settlements of refugees in the reception country were viewed as the norm by the drafters. This assumption corresponds with the reality, as some of the largest refugee camps are situated in African countries, e.g. Ethiopia, Kenya and Uganda.²⁶⁹ Read in conjunction with human rights provisions on free movement and Article 26 of the Refugee

²⁶⁰ Wood, 'Who Is a Refugee in Africa?' (n 234) 292.

²⁶¹ *ibid.* For the change of the political environment in South Africa, see Khan and Rayner (n 231).

²⁶² OAU Convention, art II (3) and (5).

²⁶³ OAU Convention, art IV.

²⁶⁴ OAU Convention, art VI.

²⁶⁵ OAU Convention, art V.

²⁶⁶ See further Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 90 ff.

²⁶⁷ Abass and Mystris (n 234) 23. See on this possibility in conjunction with Article 12 (3) of the African Charter below.

²⁶⁸ Wood, 'Who Is a Refugee in Africa?' (n 254) 294.

²⁶⁹ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 287; see further Khan and Sackeyfio (n 228).

Convention, however, Article II(6) cannot serve as a legal basis to contain refugees in large settlements.²⁷⁰

Apart from the aforementioned rights explicitly stated in the OAU Convention, its preamble also recognises the 1951 Refugee Convention. The reference creates two issues. First, it does not specify whether refugees under Article I(2) of the OAU Convention also enjoy the rights of the Refugee Convention, in case they do not fall within its refugee definition.²⁷¹ Second, it leaves open the obligations of state parties to the OAU Convention, which are not party to the Refugee Convention.²⁷² However, it has been argued that the recognition in the preamble in conjunction with the complementary nature of the OAU Convention demonstrates that the refugees under this Convention enjoy the full benefits of the Refugee Convention as well.²⁷³ Yet, many African countries that have ratified the Refugee Convention hold reservations to the right to freedom of movement and the right to work.

The African Charter, next to the principle of *non-refoulement* as set out above, holds additional rights for refugees. Article 12 of the African Charter specifically states:

1. Every individual shall have the *right to freedom of movement and residence within the borders of a State* provided he abides by the law.
2. Every individual shall have the *right to leave* any country including his own, and to return to his country. This right may only be subject to restrictions, provided for by law for the protection of national security, law and order, public health or morality.
3. Every individual shall have the right, when persecuted, *to seek and obtain asylum* in other countries in accordance with laws of those countries and international conventions.
4. A non-national *legally admitted in a territory* of a State Party to the present Charter, *may only be expelled* from it by virtue of a decision taken in accordance with the law.

²⁷⁰ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 287.

²⁷¹ Refugee Convention, art I; see further Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 124 ff; Bonaventure Rutinwa, 'Relationship between the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1969 OAU Convention on Refugees: A Historical Perspective' in Volker Türk, Alice Edwards and Cornelis Wouters (eds), *In Flight from Conflict and Violence: UNHCR's Consultations on Refugee Status and Other Forms of International Protection* (Cambridge University Press 2017); Wood, 'Who Is a Refugee in Africa?' (n 254) 294 f with further references.

²⁷² David James Cantor and Farai Chikwanha, 'Reconsidering African Refugee Law' (2019) 31 *International Journal of Refugee Law* 182, 202. These are for example the Comoros, Libya and South Sudan; Eritrea and Mauritius have signed but not ratified the OAU Convention.

²⁷³ Wood, 'Who Is a Refugee in Africa?' (n 254) 294 f with further references; see detailed analysis in Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 90 ff.

5. The *mass expulsion* of non-nationals shall be prohibited. Mass expulsion shall be that which *is aimed at national, racial, ethnic or religious groups*.

Hence, this provision not only includes a right to seek and obtain asylum in a contracting state, it also holds a protection from unlawful expulsion²⁷⁴ and mass expulsion.²⁷⁵ It stands out that Article 12 (5) of the African Charter holds a definition of mass expulsion and that this definition is based on discriminative expulsion due to nationality, race, ethnicity or religion.

The ACHPR has applied also other rights of the African Charter to refugees, such as the right to non-discrimination, the right to life, the right to human dignity, the right to liberty and security of the person, the right to access to judicial protection and the right to property.²⁷⁶ The African Charter further includes socio-economic rights, which apply to persons under the jurisdiction of state parties.²⁷⁷ The accessibility of these rights seems, however, limited.²⁷⁸ The OAU Convention, in contrast, is completely silent on civil and political and socio-economic rights for refugees.

The Women's Protocol states in Article 11 (3):

*States Parties undertake to protect asylum seeking women, refugees, returnees and internally displaced persons, against all forms of violence, rape and other forms of sexual exploitation, and to ensure that such acts are considered war crimes, genocide and/or crimes against humanity and that their perpetrators are brought to justice before a competent criminal jurisdiction.*²⁷⁹

The African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child holds additional protections for child refugees. Article 23 states:

1. States Parties to the present Charter shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that a child who is seeking refugee status or who is considered a refugee in accordance with applicable international or domestic law shall, whether unaccompanied or accompanied by parents,

²⁷⁴ See *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa (on behalf of Sierra Leonean refugees in Guinea) v. Guinea*, Comm no 249/02 (ACHPR, December 2004) para 68.

²⁷⁵ *Organisation Mondiale Contre la Torture and Others v Rwanda*, Comm no 27/89, 49/91 and 99/93 (ACHPR, 31 October 1996) para 31 f.

²⁷⁶ *Organisation Mondiale Contre la Torture and Others v Rwanda*, Comm no 27/89, 49/91 and 99/93 (ACHPR, 31 October 1996); *Institute for Human Rights and Development in Africa (on behalf of Sierra Leonean refugees in Guinea) v. Guinea*, Comm no 249/02 (ACHPR, December 2004); Gino J Naldi and Cristiano d'Orsi, 'The Role of the African Human Rights System with Reference to Asylum Seekers' in Ademola Abass and Francesca Ippolito (eds), *Regional Approaches to the Protection of Asylum Seekers: An International Legal Perspective* (Ashgate 2016) 56 f; Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 137 ff.

²⁷⁷ Compare African Charter, arts 15 ff.

²⁷⁸ Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 214) 137 ff; for South Africa see Khan and Rayner (n 231) 24 ff; Khan and Sackeyfio (n 228) 38.

²⁷⁹ Emphasis added; compare further Women's Protocol, art 10.

legal guardians or close relatives, *receive appropriate protection and humanitarian assistance in the enjoyment of the rights* set out in this Charter and other international human right and humanitarian instruments to which the States are parties.

2. States Parties shall undertake to cooperate with existing international organizations which protect and assist refugees in their efforts to protect and assist such a child and to trace the parents or other close relatives of an unaccompanied refugee child in order to *obtain information necessary for reunification with the family*.

3. Where no parents, legal guardians or close relatives can be found, the child shall be accorded the *same protection as any other child permanently or temporarily deprived of his family environment* for any reason.

4. The provisions of this Article apply *Mutatis Mutandis* to *internally displaced children* whether through natural disaster, internal armed conflicts, civil strife, breakdown of economic and social order or howsoever caused.²⁸⁰

Article 19 (1) of the Children's Charter further entitles every child with parental care and protection as well as the right to reside with its parents. Article 25 Children's Charter provides for special protection and assistance including alternative family care for children who got separated from their parents. Article 6(3) Children's Charter further guarantees the right to acquire nationality. These rights get monitored by the African Committee of Experts on the Rights and Welfare of the Child, which has not issued decisions on refugee children yet.²⁸¹

Although a comprehensive catalogue of rights according to international and regional refugee law are provided by the national legislation in South Africa, practice shows insufficient implementation also in this regard. This concerns the observation of *non-refoulement* and socioeconomic rights in particular.²⁸²

4.6 Resettlement and complementary pathways

The OAU Convention does not provide for a concrete resettlement scheme. However, Article II states:

4. Where a Member State finds difficulty in continuing to grant asylum to refugees, such Member State may appeal directly to other Member

²⁸⁰ Emphasis added.

²⁸¹ Compare, however, *Refugee Consortium of Kenya and NT v the Attorney General, the Cabinet Secretary Ministry of Interior and National Co-ordination and the Commissioner of Refugee Affairs*, Petition no 382/2014 (High Court of Kenya, 18 December 2015) para 50; Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 138 ff.

²⁸² See further Khan and Rayner (n 231) 23 ff with further references.

States and through the OAU, and such other Member States shall in the spirit of African solidarity and international co-operation take appropriate measures to lighten the burden of the Member State granting asylum.

5. Where a refugee has not received the right to reside in any country of asylum, he may be granted temporary residence in any country of asylum in which he first presented himself as a refugee *pending arrangement for his resettlement in accordance with the preceding paragraph*.²⁸³

As Sharpe concludes 'Article II(4) was significantly ahead of its time.'²⁸⁴ However, practice shows little reflection of this progressive provision so far, due to a lack of resources. Yet, Benin and Burkina Faso resettled 226 refugees under the UNHCR's Trust Fund for Enhancing Resettlement Activities and, in 2017, Rwanda offered to host evacuated asylum seekers from Libya under the ETM.²⁸⁵ In 2018, Niger also assisted UNHCR as a transit country in the evacuation of vulnerable persons from Libya under the ETM.²⁸⁶

4.7 Conclusions

The primary legal foundation of the African regional system is the OAU Convention. However, the system builds on a complementary approach in conjunction with the Refugee Convention and in reliance on regional human rights provisions, most importantly the African Charter. These provide a comprehensive framework of refugee rights, while leaving detailed regulation to the national states.

The OAU Convention explicitly intends to complement the international protection system, which results in some outstanding differences. First of all, this concerns the extended refugee definition, *inter alia*, providing for protection based on the circumstances in the country of origin as opposed to individual persecution. Furthermore, the Member States of the OAU were, at the time of drafting, evidently concerned about the stability of the region and the 'friction' refugee reception might cause.²⁸⁷ Hence, Article II(2) of the OAU Convention states that the reception of refugees is to be seen as a peaceful act.²⁸⁸ In addition, a prohibition of subversive activities for refugees was included in Article III of the OAU Convention.

The definition of *non-refoulement* in Article II(3) of the OAU Convention is broader than Article 33 of the Refugee Convention. It is, however, similar to the protection developed in by the ECtHR in Europe pursuant to Articles 2 and 3

²⁸³ Emphasis added.

²⁸⁴ Sharpe, *The Regional Law of Refugee Protection in Africa* (n 234) 76.

²⁸⁵ *ibid* 76 f.

²⁸⁶ 'Niger, sheltering Libyan refugees' (di Coopi, 2018), available at <https://www.coopi.org/en/niger-sheltering-libyan-refugees.html> accessed 7 April 2022.

²⁸⁷ Sharpe, 'Regional Refugee Regimes: Africa' (n 216) 283.

²⁸⁸ See further OAU Convention, recitals 3 ff.

ECHR.²⁸⁹ Article 5 of the African Charter links the principle of *non-refoulement* and the recognition of one's legal status with 'the respect of the dignity inherent in a human being'. The African Charter grants further generous socio-economic rights and holds specific provisions for refugees. Furthermore, Article II(4) of the OAU Convention provides for solidarity and co-operation in burden-sharing if a Member State is finding difficulty in continuing to grant asylum.

In sum, the legal provisions forming the African regional system make a progressive impression with far-reaching aims in the spirit of humanitarianism and solidarity. The evidence for implementation of these protections in practice is, to the contrary, limited with gross violations of procedural rights and many refugees being contained in large refugee camps. Despite the OAU Convention's own burden-sharing mechanism, it has been reported that the GCR has improved the situation by increasing international solidarity and thereby increasing financial means to cope with the large numbers of refugees and displaced on the continent.²⁹⁰

5 THE RIGHT OF ASYLUM IN ASIA AND THE MIDDLE EAST

As neither the Asia-Pacific nor the Middle East have binding regional instruments for the protection of refugees, this brief section provides an overview of relevant regional instruments, with a focus on ASILE countries Bangladesh and Jordan.²⁹¹

Jordan is party to the *Arab Charter on Human Rights* (Arab Charter), which is a binding instrument with provision that are relevant to refugee protection.²⁹² The *Arab Convention on Regulating Status of Refugees in the Arab Countries* has not entered into force yet, due to a lack of ratifications. The Arab Charter includes a right to political asylum in its Article 28 stating:

Everyone has the right to seek political asylum in another country in order to escape persecution. This right may not be invoked by persons facing prosecution for an offence under ordinary law. Political refugees may not be extradited.'

²⁸⁹ Compare section 2.2.

²⁹⁰ See Khan and Sackeyfio (n 228).

²⁹¹ Compare, however, non-binding recommendations in Final text of the AALCO's 1966 Bangkok Principles on the Status and Treatment of Refugees (adopted 24 June 2001) and the Arab Convention on Regulating Status of Refugees in the Arab Countries (adopted 1994, not ratified).

²⁹² Arab Charter on Human Rights 2004 (adopted 23 May 2004, entered into force 15 March 2008).

This right is also included in the list of non-derogable rights in Article 4(2) of the Arab Charter together with the right to life in Article 5 and the prohibition of torture and cruel, degrading, humiliating or inhumane treatment in Article 8.

The Arab Charter is to be interpreted in the light of other international and regional human rights obligations of the respective state according to its Article 43. Insofar, it seems to offer a wide scope of protection especially when read in conjunction with the Refugee Convention – yet only Yemen and Egypt are party to both.²⁹³ Jordan has ratified the ICCPR, ICESCR, CAT, CERD, CRC, CEDAW, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and is a member of the Bali Process.²⁹⁴ In contrast, the wording of Article 28 Arab Charter evidently raises interpretation questions as its wording seems to only include refugees for political grounds. Further, it provides for the exclusion of persons persecuted for an offense “under ordinary criminal law”, thus making the protection dependent on national provisions.

The Arab Charter has further been criticised as ineffective, because of its lack of implementation mechanisms.²⁹⁵ The Charter only foresees a reporting mechanism by the state parties to the Secretary General of the League of Arab States (LAS) (Article 48), who transmits them to the Arab Human Rights Committee (Article 45). Yet, it does not provide for an individual or state complaint mechanism. In 2014, a Statute of the Arab Court of Human Rights was adopted by the LAS. However, not only has it faced criticism in several points, such as a lack of an individual complaint mechanism, of enforcement power and of (political) independence. Also, not enough countries have ratified it for the Statute to enter into force.²⁹⁶

In the Asia-Pacific, the Bangkok Principles on the Status and Treatment of Refugees were first adopted in 1966 by the Asian-African Legal Consultative Organization, of which Bangladesh is a member, and rearticulated in 2001.²⁹⁷ The Principles, which are declaratory and non-binding in character, recognise

²⁹³ Compare Maja Janmyr and Dallal Stevens, ‘Regional Refugee Regimes: Middle East’ in Cathryn Costello, Michelle Foster and Jane McAdam (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of International Refugee Law* (Oxford, 2021) 334-351, 335.

²⁹⁴ Janmyr and Stevens, Middle East 337, 341; Declaration of the Sixth Ministerial Conference of the Bali Process on People Smuggling, Trafficking in Persons and Related Transnational Crime (‘Bali Process’) (Bali, 23 March 2016).

²⁹⁵ Wael Allam, ‘The Arab Charter on Human Rights: Main Features’ (2014) 28 *Arab Law Quarterly* 40, 62 f.

²⁹⁶ See Ahmed Almutawa, ‘The Arab Court of Human Rights and the Enforcement of the Arab Charter on Human Rights’ (2021) 21 *Human Rights Law Review* 506.

²⁹⁷ Final Text of the Asian-African Legal Consultative Organization (AALCO) 1966 Bangkok Principles on Status and Treatment of Refugees, AALCO’s 40th Session, New Delhi (adopted 24 June 2001).

the right to seek asylum and the principle of *non-refoulement*.²⁹⁸ In addition, the Principles extend the definition of a refugee beyond Article 1A of the Refugee Convention, providing:

The term “refugee” shall also apply to every person, who, owing to external aggression, occupation, foreign domination or events seriously disturbing public order in either part or the whole of his country of origin or nationality, is compelled to leave his place of habitual residence in order to seek refuge in another place outside his country of origin or nationality.²⁹⁹

Goodwin-Gill and McAdam have highlighted that for many Asian states, including Bangladesh, the Principles ‘are the only agreed statements of refugee protection principles which are applied throughout the region’.³⁰⁰

Relatedly, the 1993 Bangkok Declaration on Human Rights of 1993, to which Bangladesh is a signatory, includes some elements of refugee protection. Article 11 emphasises:

the importance of guaranteeing the human rights and fundamental freedoms of vulnerable groups such as ethnic, national, racial, religious and linguistic minorities, migrant workers, disabled persons, indigenous peoples, refugees and displaced persons³⁰¹

However, the Declaration also balances human rights against state sovereignty. Article 5 stresses: ‘the principles of respect for national sovereignty and territorial integrity as well as non-interference in the internal affairs of States, and the non-use of human rights as an instrument of political pressure’.³⁰²

6 CONCLUSIONS

This comparative working paper reveals significant differences in regional definitions of these falling under the scope of international protection. With

²⁹⁸ Articles II and III.

²⁹⁹ Article I(2).

³⁰⁰ Guy S. Goodwin-Gill and Jane McAdam, *The Refugee in International Law* (3rd ed., OUP 2007) 2013.

³⁰¹ Final Declaration of the Regional Meeting for Asia of the World Conference on Human Rights, World Conference on Human Rights, Bangkok, 29 March-2 April 1993, UN Doc A/CONF.157/PC/59 (7 April 1993).

³⁰² Final Declaration of the Regional Meeting for Asia of the World Conference on Human Rights, World Conference on Human Rights, Bangkok, 29 March-2 April 1993, UN Doc A/CONF.157/PC/59 (7 April 1993).

respect to *access to asylum*, all three regions contain an individual right to seek asylum broadly in line with the 1951 Convention. The IACtHR is notable in establishing that to ensure effectiveness, the asylum state owes a positive obligation to allow persons access to territory and asylum procedures.³⁰³

In relation to *asylum procedures*, the European asylum system has far more developed rules than the African and American regional systems. The CEAS, in particular, includes sophisticated procedural guarantees related to the allocation of responsibility, asylum procedures and reception conditions. While the IACtHR has recently set out a fairly detailed set of procedural guarantees, these judgments are not supported by regional legislation. Similarly, while the ACHPR has developed procedural guarantees based on the right to a fair trial, these are not supported by detailed regional rules.

With respect to the *scope of international protection*, both the OAU Convention and the Cartagena Declaration system provide broader conceptions of refugeehood than Europe. The definition of refugeehood contained in the OAU Convention, notably, provides protection from conflict and indiscriminate violence, an approach more suited to protecting people fleeing from generalised violence and war. Importantly, too, the African regional system does not include use of the IPA concept, acknowledging that people may flee localised risks in one part of their country of origin.

The Cartagena Declaration, though not binding law, expands the scope of protection by identifying five 'situational events' that give rise to refugeehood. These situations are based on objective and often generalised conditions in the country of origin, such as generalised violence, internal conflicts or massive violations of human rights. As a result, Cartagena provides a framework for a broader scope of protection based on general rather than individual reasons for flight.

In some contrast, within Europe both the CEAS and ECHR provide protection based on highly individualised procedures with a focus on protection from personal risk, with significant use of the internal protection alternative (IPA) concept. While the scope of European asylum law has been significantly expanded by the introduction of subsidiary protection status, it remains a highly individualised system based on the personal risk of the applicant.

With respect to the content of international protection, the CEAS provides the most detailed set of standards for the treatment of refugees after status determination. The EUQD includes a list of rights including protection from

³⁰³ Advisory Opinion OC-25/18 of 30 May 2018 Requested by the Republic of Ecuador para 122. See also *Pacheco Tineo Family v. Bolivia* (Merits, Reparations and Costs, Judgment) IACtHR Series C No 272 (25 November 2013) para 210.

refoulement, the maintenance of family unity, the issuance of residence permits and travel documents, access to employment, to education, to social welfare and healthcare, to accommodation, to freedom of movement within the territory and to integration facilities.³⁰⁴ The OAU Convention grants protection from *refoulement* including the possibility of temporary reception, protection from discrimination, a right to travel documents and a right to voluntary repatriation.³⁰⁵ The inter-American system has aligned regional protection standards with those contained in the 1951 Convention and its 1967 Protocol.

Finally, resettlement and complementary pathways on the regional level remain in the policy and not legal realm. Neither Africa nor the Americas have a dedicated regional mechanism, with practice in this area confined to the national level. Two *ad hoc* EU resettlement schemes have been undertaken since 2015, in addition to the 2016 Proposal for a Regulation on a Union Resettlement Framework. However, the prospect of a legally binding European regional resettlement mechanism remains distant.

³⁰⁴ See EUQD, arts 20-34.

³⁰⁵ OAU Convention, art V.

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